

Report on Dissemination¹ Activities

D2.4

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¹ This report also includes Communication activities carried out during the referred period (M1-M36)

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Summary

This document reports on the EPOS dissemination and communication activities² performed during the first 36 months of the EPOS IP project (M1-M36). These activities have been fulfilled strictly following the communication strategy as described in the EPOS Communication Plan (D2.1; M6 Official; M24 Internal).

Introduction

The overarching goal of EPOS's communication is to promote understanding for a full and effective exploitation of EPOS's achievements. Consequently, dissemination and communication activities must serve to raise awareness of the EPOS mission and objectives, increasing potential societal and economic impacts. Considering that, these activities have been designed and conducted to ensure effective internal and external communication targeting specific audiences. However, to be sure about the success of the performed activities, criteria for measuring and monitoring the impact of all of the communication activities have been also developed. They are specifically reported in WP2 dedicated task (2.6-Impact Analysis) and deliverables (D2.8 and D2.9, First and Second Report on Impact Analysis, respectively).

This document firstly would describe the main purpose of dissemination and communication activities and then provide an overview of the main activities performed during the first 36 months of the EPOS IP project.

This report must be considered as a dynamic document, has been drafted on M12, M24 internally. The next delivery of the report is scheduled on M48 (internal).

1. The Aim of EPOS IP Dissemination and Communication Activities

The EPOS communication strategy relies on four strategic activities: (i) **dissemination**, (ii) **communication**, (iii) **engagement** and (iv) **training**. This report concerns the first two activities: dissemination and communication, whereas the second two will be object of dedicated deliverables (D2.2 Report on stakeholder engagement [M36] and D2.6 Reports on Training Activities [M48], respectively).

The activities concerned with dissemination, aim at the public disclosure of the EPOS results, whereas communication activities mostly concern the management of the information flow from and toward EPOS. They are dedicated to deliver and/or receive specific messages to/from selected target audiences involved or to be involved in EPOS. Nevertheless, both dissemination and communication activities, also synergic with engagement and training activities, have the common objective of contributing to make the EPOS Communication Plan operational, and therefore the EPOS communication effective.

1.1. The Execution of the Communication Plan

The Communication Plan identifies and describes strategies and activities to be undertaken to ensure effective internal and external communication with the stakeholders. Therefore, all the activities must be

² Dissemination and Communication activities referred to the period M1-M36 are reported on the following documents, depending on their type: D2.2 Report on stakeholder engagement (M12 - Internal; M36 - official); D2.3 Web Portal (M3); D2.5 Report on Brokerage Activity (M24 - Internal); D2.6 Report on Training Activities (M24 - internal); D2.7 Report on Global Cooperation (M24 - Internal); D2.8 First Report on Impact analysis (M24 – Official).

performed reflecting the communication strategy described in the document, with reference to the target-audience categories identified. As already mentioned, the overarching goal of the EPOS communication is to promote the understanding for a full and effective exploitation of the EPOS achievements.

The EPOS strategy, to ensure the full operation of the Communication Plan, defines the tools dedicated to the dissemination and communication activities, plans these activities and their implementation, accordingly with specific purposes and timelines. EPOS communication channels and tools (Web; Social media; newsletter and so on) and their use, are considered as well as a part of the communication activities. All these aspects are essential for making the communication plan operational and having an impact on the audience categories identified.

Furthermore, making dissemination and communication activities well targeted, organized and monitored can contribute to the accomplishment of the EPOS IP objectives, and undeniably, to the exploitation of the EPOS IP achievements. Another aspect is monitoring them, to help identify and address any possible problem that could affect the performance of these activities. In D2.8 First Report on Impact Analysis, a variety of indicators (KPIs) have been identified to monitor and measure the impact of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken during the first two years of the project and planned for the future.

2. Disseminate and Communicate EPOS

2.1. The EPOS Website

The EPOS website (www.epos-ip.org), regularly updated, is fully active since the Preparatory Phase on December 2010 and updated in a new version layout and contents on January 2016 (M3). It contains all the information relating to the EPOS integration plan, and so the EPOS IP project. The design of the website has been streamlined to promote usability and engagement. The home page contains information about EPOS (Introducing EPOS information and video); presents the current news and events; gives links to the EPOS thematic core services web-pages; presents Twitter feeds and gives access to the EPOS official YouTube Channel.

On May 25th, 2018 following the entry into application of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the new [EPOS Privacy Policy](#) has been updated and published in the EPOS website.

All EPOS subscribers and website visitors have been informed about the aim of the GDPR by several announcements through the EPOS newsletter and the Intranet platform. In particular, they have been informed about the procedures to express the consent, about how EPOS uses personal data, and the possibility to update the personal data and preferences on the Intranet user page.

The EPOS website (Figure 1) is targeted to all the EPOS stakeholders from research communities, to policy makers and funders, private sector representatives and society.

Due to the heterogeneity of the EPOS scientific community, each TCS (Figure 2) is enabled to manage its web site area autonomously, so each solid Earth community can upload news and other general contents. The TCS areas are developed as “mini-sites” (Figure 3) meaning “sites in the site”, maintaining the global EPOS graphic design and layout.

Table 1 reports the EPOS IP website opened sessions, number of page-views, number of visitors and average of pages visited until September 2018.

Figure 4 shows three samples of the EPOS website Google Analytics statistics pages, from January 2016 until September 2018.

www.epos-ip.org

Figure 1 - The EPOS website home-page.

Figure 2 - The TCSs “mini-sites” Logos and denominations.

Figure 3 - A sample of a TCS “mini-site” Home-Page (Volcano Observations).

Table 1 - EPOS Implementation Phase website statistics (M36)

Overview - EPOS Implementation Phase website statistics - M36				
1 January - 30 September 2016	15,355 sessions	45,873-page views	9,943 new visitors	average of 3 pages visited
1 October 2016 - 30 September 2017	29,202 sessions	93,696-page views	17,316 new visitors	average of 3.21 pages visited
1 October 2017 - 30 September 2018	32,858 sessions	89,819-page views	21,275 new visitors	average of 2.73 pages visited

Audience Overview

Audience Overview

Figure 4 - Some samples of the EPOS website Google Analytics statistics from January 2016 until September 2018.

2.2. The EPOS Intranet

The EPOS intranet is a platform for EPOS knowledge management, collaboration and communications, created in November 2015 (M2). It provides an effective project management and represents an everyday communications tool for the EPOS IP project partners (the registered users are currently over 680).

The platform is structured in public and private areas (Figure 5), to facilitate the management and tracking of communications, decisions and activities at a WP level:

WP-level communication

- Messages
- Events calendar for meetings, events & deadlines
- File repository – sharing files
- Web conference tool – for WP & task calls
- Wiki

- The EPOS intranet is divided into work spaces which are generally Working Groups
- Most groups are **PUBLIC**
- Some groups are **PRIVATE**

Remember: each WP or WG has an intranet space

Figure 5 - The level of privacy linked to the group's membership (not exhaustive).

In the public groups, all content is public: messages, threads, file repository, event calendar, web conferences, but non-members can access in read-only and they cannot contribute. Table 2 shows an EPOS Intranet activity overview at M36.

In the private groups, all content is for members only, non-members cannot access any content and cannot contribute (send a message, upload a file etc.). The list of all the EPOS intranet Groups is enumerated in Table 3, together with the number of their members and posts.

As a general policy, each workspace member has read access to all groups, while the memberships in a specific group allows to start discussions threads, comment on them, upload files, set up and run web conferences, publish events on the event calendar; the framework also allows the creation of closed groups where privacy of the communication is guaranteed exclusively only to members. The majority of

workspaces are public, an approach which enables transparency and gives partners the opportunity to be always updated on project activities, even if not directly involved. The Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR), the Advisory Board (AB), Ethics Working Group (WG), the Project Development Board (PDB), and WP Leaders workspaces are private, allowing to share confidential documents and messages. By having all information in one place, the intranet facilitates partners in tracking work, in particular for reporting.

Figure 6 shows the EPOS intranet homepage and some of its functionalities.

Figure 6 - Intranet homepage and its functionalities.

Table 2 - EPOS Intranet activity overview at M36

Overview EPOS Intranet activity - M36	
Total number of registered users: 680	
Total N° Groups	84
1 January 2016 - 30 September 2016	8.290 sessions, and 1.681 visitors
1 October 2016 – 30 September 2017	8.402 sessions, and 1.643 visitors
1 October 2017 - September 2018	5.206 sessions, and 1.222 visitors

Table 3 - EPOS Intranet Group, members and posts, from January 2017 to September 2018.

Groups	Members	Posts
AAAI	46	13
AB	12	77
APIs	51	73
Architecture Group	47	10
BGR	34	229
BNSR	30	243
Documentation group	46	22
EC	6	7
EEP	11	8
Epos groups	43	4
EthicsWG	10	69
Global	680	538
GUI	50	85
HG01 Seismological Data	8	3
HG02 Geodetic data	10	3
HG03 Satellite data	7	3
HG04 Magnetic data	7	2
HG05 Geology	8	3
HG06 Episodes	18	3
HG07 Geohazards	16	3
HG08 Georesources	15	3
HG09 Geochemical data	13	5
HG10 3D/4D structural models	10	3
HG11 Analog and numerical models	10	2
HG12 Borehole data	13	3
HG13 Rock sample properties	8	3
HG14 EQ parameters	10	3
HG15 Meteo parameters	6	3
HG17 Georesource production data	10	3
HG19 Transnational Access (TNA)	17	25
HG20 Active seismic data	5	3
INGV	64	16
IPC	58	143
Messaging System	47	4
Metadata Group	51	169
Newsletter Editorial Board	17	38
PDB	18	621
PID/UID	46	5
PMO	14	89

Private space test	0	0
Requirements and Use Cases group	47	72
SCB	34	436
Support	8	1062
Support2	2	2
System Orchestrator	46	12
TCS - Communication	52	78
TCS - Financial	39	50
TCS - Harmonization	51	33
TCS - IT	61	43
TCS - Legal & Governance	37	29
TCS MSL Consortium Board	12	37
Test Group	9	29
Test-INGV	6	29
TESTING_PMO	6	1260
Women in EPOS	4	22
Workflow	48	6
WP Leaders	37	239
WP01	12	183
WP02	25	95
WP03	17	66
WP04	11	130
WP05	13	76
WP06 & WP07	65	653
WP08	78	87
WP09	54	268
WP10	52	897
WP11	87	188
WP12	26	125
WP13	19	426
WP14	53	239
WP15	45	578
WP15 Active seismic	7	5
WP15 Boreholes	20	12
WP15 Geology	3	4
WP15 Georesources	2	4
WP15 Models	6	5
WP15 Rock Sample Properties	4	4
WP16	69	392
WP16 Analogue Modelling	18	55
WP16 Analytical	20	28

WP16 Paleomag	15	32
WP16 Rock physics	18	10
WP16 Task Leaders	18	276
WP17	15	65

2.3. The EPOS Newsletter

EPOS newsletter has the aim of communicate news, events and other information relevant to the EPOS Community, the solid Earth science domain and beyond. It provides updates on a wide range of project-related collaborations with the scope to generate enthusiasm and enhance readability.

The EPOS Newsletter should be intended as a strategic outreach and a dissemination tool to reach the different communities involved in the EPOS integration plan as well as to circulate information that might attract readers and users from different domains.

The newsletter is managed by an Editorial Board composed by an Editor in Chief and a Scientific Committee and benefits of a professional graphic designer and of the technical support from the PMO. It is published 4 times a year (special issues are foreseen to emphasize particular EPOS achievements or events) and, currently, is sent to a mailing list of 1106 subscribers by the MailChimp tool and published in the EPOS website at the EPOS newsletter page: <https://www.epos-ip.org/news-press/epos-ip-newsletter> (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Respectively, the EPOS IP Newsletter page on the EPOS Website, and a sample of the newsletter template.

The EPOS IP Newsletter is composed by several sections:

- 1) **Articles.** This section is dedicated to arguments deserving particular consideration within the EPOS community, e.g. the infrastructures, and EPOS related projects. It addresses global grand challenges in Earth science.
- 2) **News.** Workshops, work-meetings and on-going EPOS IP activities are promoted in this section. Articles and news contain figures and/or pictures covered by copyright, also catalogued in the EPOS website by Flickr account.
- 3) **Highlights.** One hot topic or EPOS achievements that deserve to be shared with the Community.
- 4) **TOP TIPS from the EPOS IT team.** This section fosters the EPOS technological and ICT innovation and in particular has the goal to explain ideas or plans putting forward for consideration.
- 5) **Communication.** In this section links to different EPOS website pages are available, e.g.: OUTREACH materials, GLOSSARY, USEFUL Links, EPOS Community intranet.
- 6) **NOTEWORTHY from the WEB.** Here interesting, significant or unusual files, videos or events that have appeared on the web are emphasized.

During the 3rd year of the project to attract more the interest of new and existing readers the EPOS newsletter layout with more pictures and an Index of contents has been updated (Figure 8), a subject line of the email i.e. with the use of the name of person, and a brief text summarizing the important content of the newsletter has been introduced; as well the Re-sending of the newsletter by email (1 or 2 times) only to people who didn't open the first time. The statistics shows the increase of subscribers and the maintenance of the average of readers.

To maintain a high level of articles and communicating the EPOS innovation and how it is adding value to existing national research infrastructures all the TCSs and IT communication contact persons have been involved in the Editorial Board (Table 4).

The newsletter allows to get in contact with EPOS social media: twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube channel.

All Articles, Highlights and TOP TIPS are archived on the EPOS website and available in pdf format (<https://www.epos-ip.org/news-press/newsletters>); each past issues of the newsletter is published in the EPOS website at the EPOS newsletter page: <https://www.epos-ip.org/news-press/epos-ip-newsletter> and spread out through the EPOS social media channels. Table 5 presents an overview of the newsletter statistical data at M36, and Table 6 shows statistical information related to the number of subscribers, readers, and average open rate. Annex 1 lists the Newsletter editions and their contents.

Figure 8 - The EPOS IP Newsletter layout updated on July 2018.

Table 4 - The Editorial Board Members at M36

The Editorial Board of the EPOS newsletter	
<p>Editor in Chief Silvia Filosa INGV, Italy (PMO, WP02)</p>	<p>Scientific Committee Grzegorz Lizurek IGF PAS, Poland (WP02); Nataša Ravbar ZRC SAZU, Slovenia (WP02); Karolina Branicka IGF PAS, Poland (WP14 communication contact person); Carlo Cauzzi SED ETH, Zurich; Frederique Mojon Lumier BRGM France (WP15 communication contact person); Consiglia Rasulo IREA-CNR, Italy (WP12 communication contact person); Lílian Féres UBI, Portugal (WP10 communication contact person); Karen Tellefsen UiB, Norway (WP06&07 communication contact person); Laura Platt BGS, UK (WP02 & WP17 communication contact person); Maria Letizia Mari TRUST-IT Services, Italy (WP02)</p>
<p>Graphics Barbara Angioni INGV, Italy (PMO, WP02)</p>	
<p>IT Support Luca Postpischl INGV, Italy (PMO, WP02)</p>	

Table 5 - Overview of the Newsletter statistical data at M36

N° Newsletter Published	N° Articles	N° Subscribers	Authors of articles	
			Male	Female
12	72	1134	78	64

Table 6 - Overview of the Newsletter mailChimp statistical data at M36

Overview M36 - EPOS newsletter	
Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1134	
Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
39,71%	385
Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
12,89%	123,75
Overview M24 - EPOS newsletter	
Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1106	
Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
38,48%	380
Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
10,68%	107,75
Overview M12 - EPOS newsletter	
Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1029	
% Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
43,50%	388,6
% Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
15,90%	141,6
Overview Preparatory Phase - EPOS newsletter	
Total number of subscribed contacts: 540	
% Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
40,30%	213
% Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
16,90%	89

2.4. The EPOS Social Media

Nowadays, social networking and communities are amazingly trendy and in vogue. The undeniable power of social media is to allow the creation of a virtual community where there is the capability to share and find information, express opinions, organize events, promote work, meet people. Indeed, social media offer the remarkable opportunity to communicate directly and get in contact with people who share our interests but are far beyond our habitual community. Therefore, “going social” is not only cool: it actually works for efficient communications and outreach. As a matter of fact, by using social media EPOS will manage to reach audiences who have less interest in conventional media channels and talk with people whose attention cannot be easily captured writing scientific articles and project deliverables.

There are a wide array of social media platforms that can be adopted, each with its pros and cons. Although participating in social media may seem a “young” and spontaneous activity, EPOS cannot just “go social”: in order to fully exploit the potential of social media, EPOS must first devise a coherent communication strategy taking into account many key variables.

The EPOS IP approach for selecting suitable “social channels” has considered the popularity of the platform, the typology of end-users, the level of engagement and continuity required for the specific platform. By using these “keywords” the choices, predictably, were:

- **Facebook**, the most popular social network featuring 1.49 billion monthly active users with its highly interactive platform and probably the best channel for engaging a very wide audience; The link to the EPOS Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/EPOS-European-Plate-Observing-System-155473037830465/>
- **Twitter**, one of the most popular social networks in Europe is an online social networking service that enables users to send and read short 140-character messages. The link to the EPOS Twitter page is: <https://twitter.com/EPOSeu>
- **LinkedIn**, the premier “social network for business”. The link to the LinkedIn EPOS page is: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/epos-european-plate-observing-system-63a85412a/>

Moreover, considering that 40% of people will respond better to visual information than to plain text, the following channels will improve EPOS visibility:

- **YouTube**, the largest user-driven video content provider in the world with over a billion users and a major platform for disseminating multimedia information. The link to the YouTube EPOS page is: <https://www.youtube.com/user/eposeu>
- **SlideShare**, a Web 2.0 based slide hosting service where users can upload files privately or publicly; The link to the SlideShare is: https://www.slideshare.net/EPOS_IP (to be implemented).
- **Flickr**, a hosting service where users can share photos. The link to the EPOS Flickr page is <https://www.flickr.com/photos/eposeu/>

All these social channels are already active with links on the EPOS website homepage.

In order to engage regularly with followers in the first year, EPOS approached “softly” to social media using and implementing only some of the channels listed above (Facebook; Twitter). During the second and third year, EPOS communication team organized and scheduled weekly plans of tweets and texts to be posted on Twitter and LinkedIn and, created automatic procedures that repost news from the Web site, tweets and images from other social channels such as Flickr or Facebook. EPOS developed communication strategies to engage the EPOS TCS communities and EPOS stakeholders taking full advantage of these powerful media. EPOS is dedicating time and efforts to continuously implement and update all the social channels listed above with new ideas. In particular to those social channels such as SlideShare, YouTube, and Flickr not still *widely used*, involving the EPOS community to feed contents distributing EPOS vision and achievements.

Having followers who are popular in fields that are relevant to the EPOS activities, ensures our communication receive wide broadcasting to an interested audience, which induces a rapid growth multiplier effect. Table 7 presents an overview of the statistical data related to EPOS IP Social Media in general, insted Table 8 focuses on the Linkedin posts. Figures 9, and 10 respectively present the EPOS IP Twitter account home-page and some examples of posts on the EPOS IP facebook page.

Table 7 - Overview of the EPOS Implementation Phase social media numbers - M36

Overview Implementation Phase - EPOS social media numbers - M36				
Twitter	Facebook	Linkedin	YouTube	Flickr
Tweets	Follower	Posts	17 Video	Pictures
2191	342	19	10 Playlists	502
Follower	Likes	Connections	40 Subscribers	Views
854	335	2527	5194 Views	36.026

Table 8 - Overview of the EPOS Linkedin Posts - M36

Title	Views	Likes
EPOS-ERIC, soon a reality	39 + 5 reshares + 2 comments	21
Validation and Prioritization of the EPOS Service Provision	30 + 1 reshare	16
EPOS-TCS Volcano Observations makes hazard information accessible and searchable	40 + 1 reshare	30
EPOS in GEO	41 + 2 reshares	23
ESM and RRSM - two world class strong motion databases for seismologists and engineers	57 + 1 reshare	7
From Crystals to Mountains: the Multi-scale Laboratories in EPOS	79 + 3 reshares	45
The EPOS contribution to innovation and excellence in science	100	25
Wondering what the DDSS Master Table is and what EPOS is up to?	52	2
EPOS: developing the integrated infrastructure for Earth Science across Europe and training the next generation of solid earth scientists	66	11
EPOS: Driving Science	107	18
EPOS: Who benefits?	58	2
Near Fault Observatories in Europe: the road of integration	80	4
The EPOS Legal Entity	35	9
EPOS IP: a collaborative effort for multidisciplinary integration of data & core services from different solid earth sciences & distributed research	78 + 2 reshares	5
Thoughts about the role and ethics of scientific communication, today	72 + 1 reshare	2
Find your way in the EPOS architecture	68 + 1 reshare	2
The EPOS Implementation Phase project Where are we now?	89	-
EPOS a long-term plan for solid Earth science in Europe	84	1
EPOS - The European Plate Observing System	56	1

Figure 9 - the EPOS IP Twitter account home-page.

Your 5 Most Recent Posts

Reach: Organic / Paid | Post Clicks | Reactions, Comments & Shares

Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement	Promote
09/20/2018 5:17 pm	The core #stakeholders and their main contributions has been the	🔒	🌐	55	0 1	Boost Post
09/20/2018 5:17 pm	The @EPOSu INFO-DAY included a visit to downtown #Ljubljana focused on	🔒	🌐	86	9 4	Boost Post
09/20/2018 1:17 pm	At our Open! conference next week, we will have both of the	🔒	🌐	60	0 0	Boost Post
09/12/2018 10:06 am	#EPOSu has been officially promoted as a landmark; the	🔒	🌐	76	6 1	Boost Post
09/12/2018 10:06 am	I liked a @YouTube video https://t.co/L4jdr908Yo ESFRI	🔒	🌐	44	6 1	Boost Post

See All Posts

Figure 10 - Examples of posts on the EPOS IP facebook page.

2.5. Publications

During the period M1-M36 a number of publications were produced by the EPOS community members (Table 9).

Publications include:

- scientific articles published in scientific journals;
- presentations at conferences and other events;
- scientific publications on the World Wide Web;
- articles published in the EPOS newsletter or in other channels of communications such as press release articles.

Table 9 - Overview of the EPOS IP publications at M36

Overview - EPOS IP publications and presentations performed by WPs (1-2, 6-17) - M36				
Total number of publications and presentations: 139				
	2015	2016	2017	2018

EPOS IP Work Packages (1-2; 6-17)	4	33	44	37
EPOS IP Members	4	9	6	2
	8	42	50	39

A full list of publications is reported in Annex 2.

2.6. Events

During the first two years (M1-M36) of the EPOS IP project, the community has been active organizing meetings, workshops and conferences within the EPOS community and also participating actively to meetings, events, general assemblies organised by diverse organizations. A brief description of events, divided into Internal Events and External Event, is provided in the text below, whereas a detailed list is available in Annex 3.

Table 10 enumerates the EPOS IP project events per Work Package at M36, divided into events organized by EPOS and events where WPs were involved as TCS and Community.

Internal Events

Internal Events are referred to the events organised by EPOS within the EPOS community.

Interaction and effective internal communication have been ensured via the organisation of periodic meetings. Some of them scheduled to regularly monitor the progresses of the EPOS initiative as a whole (e.g. Board of Government Representatives meetings, Advisory Board and Ethics Working Group meetings). Others instead, organised strictly in line with the EPOS IP project activities by assessing technical, scientific, legal and financial results and discuss about any potential contingency plan (e.g. IPC, PBD and SCB meetings; TCS-ICS workshops, meetings internal to each specific community, such as the IT team meetings, and the 10 Thematic Core Services).

External Events

External Events refers to the events attended by EPOS.

The EPOS community, considering its complexity and heterogeneity, also took part to a number of initiatives outside the EPOS framework. These activities are particularly important to disseminate the EPOS vision and goals. One of them is the European Geophysical Union (EGU) General Assembly held in Vienna every year in spring time. The EGU GA, indeed, by bringing together over 11,000 scientists in the Earth, planetary, and space sciences from all over the world, is the best window to disseminate the EPOS vision not only to the solid Earth science communities. EPOS participates to EGU with its own booth, offering dedicated sessions, organising Splinter and TownHall meetings and also, participating to other sessions of relevance for the initiative (Figure 11).

Figure 11 – EPOS at EGU: respectively, a demonstration at the EPOS IP EGU Booth, and the participation of Massimo Cocco, EPOS IP Project Coordinator, presenting EPOS IP project and its achievements.

Table 10 - The EPOS Implementation Phase events per Work Package at M36

Overview - EPOS Implementation Phase events per Work Package - M36									
Total number of events: 587									
WP	Events organised by EPOS - M12	Events EPOS participated to - M12	Tot	Events organised by EPOS - M24	Events EPOS participated to - M24	Tot	Events organised by EPOS - M36	Events EPOS participated to - M36	Tot
WP1/2	24	32	56	26	23	49	17	12	29
WP3	2	2	4	2	0	2	/	3	3
WP4	/	/	0	/	1	1	/	3	3
WP5	2	1	3	/	1	1	/	3	3
WP6/7*	2	3	5	7	11	18	1	4	5
WP8	12	7	19	9	9	18	4	7	11
WP9	3	17	20	1	7	8	3	4	7
WP10	2	8	10	1	7	8	2	13	15
WP11	1	6	7	3	7	10	2	6	8
WP12	5	15	20	3	9	12	4	7	11
WP13	4	9	13	3	6	9	1	7	8
WP14	5	23	28	3	8	11	6	12	18
WP15	5	15	20	4	21	25	1	11	12
WP16	6	13	19	3	20	23	4	13	17
WP17	2	3	5	1	4	5	2	6	8
			229			200			158

* Note: WP6 and the WP7 organize teleconferences on a montly-base

2.7. Dissemination and outreach material

The EPOS brand, which means its design, logo, TCSs logos and the other features that distinguishes EPOS, has been created by the EPOS graphic designer during the Preparatory Phase, constructing an image that could specifically identifies EPOS. The EPOS Logo and the design for the EPOS Pin are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Respectively, the EPOS IP Logo, and the design for the EPOS Pin.

Over time, EPOS image has become associated with a high level of credibility, quality, and satisfaction of the stakeholders, so in the current Implementation Phase, the strategy of maintaining EPOS brand, has been adopted.

EPOS designed and produced a number of promotional materials to support communication and dissemination activities, with the following aim:

- **inform about EPOS:** brochures, flyers, banners, videos are created and distributed to inform meeting attendants about project achievements, challenges, organization, activities, and, more in general, about the EPOS mission and goals.
- **facilitate meetings professionally:** posters, banners, programmes, badges were produced to welcome the meeting attendants, inform them, facilitate their participations to the meeting.
- **promote the EPOS communication channels:** all the EPOS communication channels / media are promoted on the material distributed during conferences and meetings. Examples are links to the public website, the EPOS Intranet, the newsletter, and social media.

Apart from printed material (brochures, flyers, posters), further products and gadgets have been made to advertise EPOS (to be distributed mainly during official meetings and conferences) and to direct people to the digital EPOS communication channels. The outreach material produced is enumerated in Table 11.

Table 11 - The EPOS Implementation Phase outreach material

Overview of EPOS IP outreach material created and disseminated during the official EPOS events - M36				
	Flyers/Brochres	Logo & Corporate	Posters	Gadgets
M12 (2015-2016)	4	2	4	Pins, stickers, pens
M24 (2016-2017)	14	12	5	Block notes, pens, bags
M36 (2017- 2018)	16	6	7	Luggage Tag, bags, pens

Examples of the EPOS dissemination and outreach material are reported below.

2.7.1 Samples of EPOS IP Dissemination and Outreach Material

Video “Introducing EPOS”

Viable solutions to tackle solid Earth grand challenges

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ORbPiESluUg>

The EPOS logo

EPOS IP headed paper

Outreach material (flyers, posters, gadgets); some examples.

EPOS A LONG TERM PLAN for the INTEGRATION of RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES for SOLID EARTH SCIENCE

PARTNERS

- Belgium
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Iceland
- Ireland
- Italy
- Netherlands
- Norway
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Turkey
- United Kingdom
- ORFEUS/KNMI
- EMSC

ASSOCIATE PART.

- Austria
- Slovakia
- Bulgaria (under negotiation)
- ESA
- EUROGEO SURVEYS
- GEM

EPoS EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

Integrates national and transnational research infrastructures for solid Earth science
 for seamless access to pan-European data and services

Guarantees open access to multidisciplinary Research Infrastructures
 for cross-disciplinary and transnational research

Creates novel e-infrastructure and integrated core services
 for a multidisciplinary community of users

Fosters scientific, technological and IoT innovation
 for successfully addressing global Grand Challenges in Earth science

Improves geo-hazard assessment, risk mitigation, and sustainable management of georesources
 for a safe and prosperous society

EPoS EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

EPOS EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

A LONG TERM PLAN FOR THE INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES FOR SOLID EARTH SCIENCE IN EUROPE

EPoS EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

EPoS EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

EPoS EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

Images for diverse purposes (articles, reports, website, etc.)

Sample of TCS and WPs Logos

EPOS Website QRcode

3. ANNEXES

The Annexes to the document are the following:

- Annex 1: List of Newsletter editions and their contents
- Annex 2: List of Publications
- Annex 3: List of EPOS IP events

ANNEX 1. List of Newsletter Editions and Contents

Overview M36 - EPOS newsletter Editions and contents			
N°	Publication title	Authors	Title of articles
1	First issue n.00, February 2016	PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS announcements and news
2	issue:01 /july 2016	Massimo Cocco, INGV, Italy	Dear Reader, Welcome to the EPOS Newsletter! New releases for the implementation phase!
		Massimo Cocco, INGV, Ital	From the EPOS Conception to the EPOS Implementation Phase
		Stanislaw Lasocki, Beata Orlecka-Sikora, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland	Integrated approach to geophysical hazards induced by exploration and exploitation of georesources - to facilitate the way of attaining excellence
		Vicky Hards, BGS, United Kingdom	The Ultimate Earth a future Flagship programme of Horizon 2020 Future and Emerging Technologies
		Vicky Hards, BGS, United Kingdom	Earth Science Europe the next steps: Towards an Earth Science Board and a voice in Europe for Earth Science
		Season's Greetings	
		Florian Haslinger	EPOS at EGU 2016: a booth full of people, a successful session
		PMO, INGV, Italy	Meeting of the EPOS Board of Government Representatives (BGR)
3	issue: 02/ October 2016	Keith G. Jeffery, Massimo Cocco, Kuvvet Atakan, Matt Harrison, Daniele Bailo	The EPOS vision on EOSC
		Stefano Salvi	The GEO Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory initiative
		Sabrina Bozzoli and PMO	EPOS IP project first anniversary: towards the validation phase
		Massimo Cocco	The relevance of data integration during the August 24th 2016 earthquake in Central Apennines (Italy)
		Keith G. Jeffery	INTEROPERABILITY, PIDs and EPOS

		Lauro Chiaraluce Gaetano Festa Dragos Tataru John Clinton	Near Fault Observatories in Europe: the road of integration. Why do we need NFOs?
		Frédérique Mojon Lumier	What is EPOS “Geological Data and Modelling” Thematic Core Service (TCS) about?
		Florian Haslinger	EPOS Seismology at the General Assembly Meeting of the European Seismological Commission, 5 - 9 September 2016, Trieste, Italy
4	special issue: 03/ December 2016	PMO, INGV, Italy	Season's Greetings
5	issue: 01/ January 2017	Keith G. Jeffery	Outcomes of the WP06 - 07 IT TEAM meeting
		Elisa Calignano WP16 team	From crystals to mountains: the Multi-scale laboratories Thematic Core Service (TCS)
		Alberto Michelini Delia Arnold-Arias Gerhard Wotawa	ARISTOTLE - All Risk Integrated System TOWARDS The hoListic Early-warning
		PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS @ EGU 2017, session and booth
		Massimo Cocco, Carmela Freda, Daniele Bailo	The EPOS contribution to innovation and excellence in science
		Keith G. Jeffery	What is Metadata in EPOS?
6	issue: 02/ April 2017	PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS @ the European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2017
		Kuvvet Atakan, Daniele Bailo, Keith Jeffery and Matt Harrison	Integrated Core Services (ICS) system demonstrator in Prague Integration Workshop
		Agata Sangianantoni, Carmela Freda, Massimo Cocco	The Board of Governmental Representatives approved the STEP1 submission of the EPOS ERIC establishment
		Keith Jeffery, Daniele Bailo	TOP TIPS - Virtual Research Environments, Science Gateways and Virtual Laboratories
		Andrea Tommasi	The H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie CREEP Innovative Training Network meets EPOS

		Lucia Luzi, Alberto Michelini, Rodolfo Puglia John Clinton, Carlo Cauzzi Reinoud Sleeman	ESM and RRSN - two world class strong motion databases for seismologists and engineers
		Keith Jeffery Daniele Bailo Kuvvet Atakan Matthew Harrison	Demonstrating ICS-C Functionalities
7	issue: 03/ July 2017	WP6&7	The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) concept and its impact on Research Infrastructures
		Grzegorz Lizurek, Karolina Chodzińska	Anthropogenic seismicity workshops
		PMO, INGV, Italy	The 9th Meeting of the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures (GRI)
		PMO, INGV, Italy	The 9th Meeting of the Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR)
		PMO, INGV, Italy	The 2nd Meeting of the Board of National Scientific Representatives (BNSR)
		Alberto Michelini	The Milano and Rome EPOS harmonization meetings
		Lilian Féres	GLASS is a unique open access platform for Earth science research
		Marti Michèle	SERA and EPOS: a perfect match
		Claire André	blueSeis, a revolution in the history of geosciences!
		Roberto Basili	Probabilistic TSUNAMI hazard MAPS for the NEAM Region: the TSUMAPS-NEAM Project
		8	issue: 04/ October 2017
Massimo Cocco, Lilli Freda, Kuvvet Atakan, Joern Lauterjung, Kauzar Saleh Contell	Validation and Prioritization of the EPOS Service Provision		
PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS @ the EGU 2018 General Assembly in Vienna, 8 - 13 April 2018		
PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS INFO-DAY in the Eastern Adriatic Area		
Jean Robert Grasso	"Sismo-Dance" Workshop-Performance		

		Florian Haslinger	The PSHA workshop outcomes
		Michela Vellico	Cooperation with ECCSEL
		Sara Barsotti	EPOS-TCS Volcano Observations makes hazard information accessible and searchable
9	special issue: 05/ December 2017	PMO, INGV, Italy	Season's Greetings
10	issue: 01/ January 2018	PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS is on its way to Step 2 submission of the EPOS-ERIC
		PMO, INGV, Italy	EPOS session and booth @ the EGU 2018 in Vienna, 8-13 April 2018
		Kuvvet Atakan, Daniele Bailo, Matthew Harrison, Keith Jeffery, Jan Michalek, Karen Tellefsen	Status update from the EPOS WP6 and 7 IT Team
		Federica Magnoni, Emanuele Casarotti Iraklis Klampanos	DARE to tame the Extremes
		Silvia Peppoloni, Giuseppe Di Capua	The Cape Town Statement on Geoethics and the IAPG network
		Elisa Calignano Emilio L. Pueyo Morer Matthias Rosenau Fred Beekman	First impressions EPOS Multi-scale laboratories Trans-national access pilot program
11	issue: 02/ April 2018	Massimo Cocco, Carmela Freda	EPOS-ERIC, soon a reality
		Daniele Bailo, Karen Tellefsen	EPOS Data policy and the FAIR principles
		Laura Baracchi, Florian Haslinger	Winding up after an exciting EGU2018 week in Vienna
		Stanka Šebela, Giovanna Maracchia, Lilli Freda, Massimo Cocco, Grzegorz Lizurek	EPOS Info-Day, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 29 - 30 May, 2018

		Aude Chambodut Simon Flower Pavel Hejda , Maxim Smirnov Alan Thomson Ari Viljanen	The Geomagnetic field between Earth's core and space: how the Geomagnetic Observations "EPOS Thematic Core Services" (TCS) address the various sources of the Geomagnetic field
		Dorota Olszewska, Grzegorz Lizurek and EPOS PL team	EPOS PL polish national contribution towards EPOS infrastructure
12	issue: 03/ July 2018	Chris Card, Christian Rønnevik, Xiaoliang Wang	New developments of the EPOS-ICS-C GUI, Graphical User Interface
		Lilian Féres	EPOS TCS GNSS Data and Products represented at the 36th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission in Malta, 2 - 7 September 2018
		Frédérique Mojon	EPOS involved in the process of open standards implementation for the scientific community
		Karolina Chodzińska Branicka	EPOS Thematic Core Services Anthropogenic Hazards (TCS AH) (WP14) Workshop and Annual Meeting outcomes
		Stanka Šebela	EPOS INFO-DAY outcomes, 29 - 30 May 2018, Ljubljana, Slovenia
		Florian Haslinger	EPOS Seismology activities at the ESC 2018 in Malta, 2 - 7 September 2018
		Machiel Bos	Quality Controlled TCS GNSS Data and Products
		Luca Trani and the EPOS-ORFEUS-CC Team	The EPOS - ORFEUS Competence Centre in EOSC-hub
		Elisa Calignano Reinoud Sleeman Anke Dählmann Martyn Drury	EPOS-NL: the Netherlands contribution to EPOS
		Joao Fonseca Andreas Reitbrock Aude Chambodut	Validation of EPOS services

ANNEX 2 - List of publications and presentations

List of publications and presentations performed by WP1 and WP2				
Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Presentation	European Plate Observing System (EPOS): Integrating Thematic Services for Solid Earth Science	Atakan, K., Bailo, D., and EPOS Consortium	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	17-22 April 2016
Presentation	Importance of an integrated and sustainable solid Earth Infrastructure for Europe: European Plate Observing System (EPOS)	Atakan, K. and the EPOS Consortium	MarSite Supersites Project Final Meeting, Vienna, Austria	22 April 2016
Presentation	Ethics issues and data provisions: evidence and challenges in European Plate Observing System (EPOS)	Cocco, M., Freda C., Haslinger, F., Atakan, K. and the EPOS Consortium	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	17-22 April 2016
Presentation	Services for Solid Earth Science	Cocco, M., Atakan, K., Pedersen, H., and EPOS Consortium	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	17-22 April 2016
Presentation	Implementing European Plate Observing System (EPOS) Infrastructure	Elger, K., Lauterjung, J., Ulbricht, D., Cocco, M., Atakan, K., Bailo, D., Glaves, H., and Jeffrey, K.	SciDataCon 2016: Advancing the Frontiers of Data in Research. Conference arranged as part of the International Data Week Denver, Colorado, USA	11-13 September 2016
Presentation	Setting the stage for the EPOS ERIC: Integration of the legal, governance and financial framework	Atakan, K., Bazin, P-L., Bozzoli, S., Freda, C., Giardini, D., Hoffmann, T., Kohler, E., Kontkanen, P., Lauterjung, J., Pedersen, H., Saleh, K., and Sangianantoni, A.	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	Ethical implication of providing scientific data and services to diverse stakeholders: the case of the EPOS research infrastructure	Freda, C., Atakan, K., and Cocco, M.	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Article	Integration of heterogeneous data, software and services in Solid Earth Sciences: the EPOS system design and roadmap for the building of Integrated Core Services	Bailo, Daniele, Rossana Paciello, Riccardo Rabissoni, Manuela Sbarra, Valerio Vinciarelli	Rapporti Tecnici INGV ISSN 2039-7941, anno 2018, N. 393	2018
Other publication	The EPOS infrastructure: a novel solution for data and service provision in solid Earth science	Carmela Freda, Massimo Cocco, and Epos Consortium	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8-13 April 2018
Other publication	Moving towards EPOS ERIC: Integration of the legal, governance and financial framework	Bazin Pierre-Louis, Saleh Kauzar, Kuvvet Atakan, Sabrina Bozzoli, Carmela Freda, Domenico Giardini, Thomas Hoffmann, Elisabeth Kohler, Pirjo Kontkanen, Jörn Lauterjung, Helle Pedersen, and Agata Sangianantoni	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8-13 April 2018
List of publications and presentations performed by WP6 & WP7				
Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Article	European Plate Observing System and the Arctic.	Atakan, K., Bjerrum, L.W., Bungum, H., Dehls, J., Kaynia, A., Keers, H., Kierulf, H., Kværna, T., Langeland, T., Lindholm, C., Maupin, V., Ottemöller, L., Sørensen, M.B., and Yuen, M.Y.	Arctic, Vol. 68 (Suppl. 1)	2015

Article	Using open research data for public policy making: Opportunities of Virtual Research Environments	Zuiderwijk, A., Jeffery, K., Bailo, D., & Yin, Y.	Conference on E-Democracy and Open Government (CeDEM), Krems an der Donau, Austria	2016
Article	Virtual Research Environments: Obtaining New Insights by Sharing Open Data for Interdisciplinary Research Purposes	Anneke Zuiderwijk, Marijn Janssen, Yi Yin, Keith Jeffery, Daniele Bailo	Conference for E-Democracy and Open Government	2016
Article	Mapping solid earth Data and Research Infrastructures to CERIF	Bailo, D., Nayembil, M., Spinuso, A., Trani, L., Ulbricht, D., & Jeffery, K. G.	CRIS 2016 Conference, June 8-11 2016, St Andrews, Scotland.	2016
Newsletter article	DDSS Master Table and ICS developments	EPOS IT Team	The EPOS Newsletter issue 01	July 2016
Presentation	European Plate Observing System – _Norway (EPOS-N): Integrating the Norwegian Solid Earth Data	Atakan, K., Tellefsen, K., and the EPOS-Consortium	Oral presentation at the Norwegian Geological Society (NGF) Winter Conference. Oslo, Norway	9-11 January 2017
Presentation	European Plate Observing System Implementation Phase (EPOS-IP): a comprehensive e-Infrastructure for Solid Earth Science	Atakan, K., Tellefsen, K., and the EPOS-Consortium	Poster presentation at the Norwegian Geological Society (NGF) Winter Conference. Oslo, Norway	9-11 January 2017
Presentation	FAIR friendly research data catalogues: How far are we?	Bailo, D.	BlueBRIDGE workshop	03-apr-17
Presentation	EPOS data and service provision	Bailo, D., Jeffery, K., Atakan, K., and Harrison, M.	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	VRE4EIC: A Reference Architecture and Components for Research Access	Bailo, D., Jeffery, K., Atakan, K., and Harrison, M.	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	EPOS IP – _Data, Data Products, Services and Software (DDSS Master Table)	Michalek, J., Atakan, K., and the EPOS-IP WP6&7 Team	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	Women in EPOS: the role of women in a large pan-European Research Infrastructure for Solid Earth sciences	Elisa Calignano, Carmela Freda, and Laura Baracchi	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	Building a federated data infrastructure for integrating the European Supersites	Carmela Freda, Massimo Cocco, Giuseppe Puglisi, Sven Borgstrom, Kristin Vogfjord, Freysteinn Sigmundsson, Semih Ergintav, Nurcan Meral Ozel, and Epos Consortium	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	EPOS/VERCE ..	Daniele Bailo	European Open Science Cloud – Science Demonstrators and Pilots 13 Sept Pisa	September 2017
Article	EPOS – European Plate Observing System: Applying the VRE4EIC Virtual Research Environment Model in the Solid Earth Science Domain	Daniele Bailo, Manuela Sbarra	ERCIM News, Volume 2017	2017
Newsletter article	INTEROPERABILITY, PIDs and EPOS	Keith G. Jeffery	The EPOS Newsletter issue 02	October 2016
Newsletter article	Progress in EPOS Authentication and Authorisation Solutions	Tomasz Szepieniec, Daniele Bailo Kuvvet Atakan Keith Jeffery	The EPOS Newsletter issue 04	October 2017
Newsletter article	Status update from the EPOS WP6 and 7 IT Team	Kuvvet Atakan, Daniele Bailo, Matthew Harrison, Keith Jeffery, Jan Michalek and Karen Tellefsen	The EPOS Newsletter issue 01	January 2018
Newsletter article	EPOS Data policy and the FAIR principles	Daniele Bailo, Karen Tellefsen, WP06 - WP07 team	The EPOS Newsletter issue 02	apr-18
Presentation	Achieving integration through EPOS	D. Bailo, R. Paciello, JB Roquencourt and V. Vinciarelli	IWSG 2018 – 10th International Workshop on Science Gateways, 13-15 June 2018, Edinburgh, Scotland	13-15 June 2018

Presentation	EPOS: integration of heterogeneous data and services in the Solid Earth domain	Keith Jeffery and Daniele Bailo	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Presentation	Integrated Core Services Architecture.	Daniele Bailo and Keith Jeffery	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Other publication	Representing Core Concepts for solid-Earth sciences with DCAT – the EPOS-DCAT Application Profile	Luca Trani, Rossana Paciello, Manuela Sbarra, and Damian Ulbricht and the EPOS IT Team	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Other publication	EPOS-IP – DDSS Master Table and Granularity Database	Jan Michalek, Xiaoliang Wang, Kuvvet Atakan, and Christian Rønnevik and the WP6+WP7 of EPOS-IP project team	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Newsletter article	New developments of the EPOS-ICS-C GUI, Graphical User Interface	Chris Card, Christian Rønnevik, Xiaoliang Wang	The EPOS Newsletter issue 03	30/07/18
Newsletter article	The EPOS - ORFEUS Competence Centre in EOSC-hub	Luca Trani and the EPOS-ORFEUS-CC Team	The EPOS Newsletter issue 03	30/07/18
Article	Establishing Core Concepts for Information-Powered Collaborations.	Luca Trani, Malcolm Atkinson, Daniele Bailo, Rossana Paciello, Rosa Filgueira	Future Generation Computer Systems, Volume 89, 2018, Pages 421-437, ISSN 0167-739X, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.07.005	2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP8

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Article	Why Seismic Networks Need Digital Object Identifiers	Evans et al.	Eos, 96	08/10/15
Article	Introducing the European Rapid Raw Strong - Motion Database	Cauzzi et al.	Seismological Research Letters, Volume 87 number 4	July/August 2016
Article	The Engineering Strong - Motion Database: A Platform to Access Pan - European Accelerometric Data	Luzi et al	Seismological Research Letters, Volume 87 number 4	July/August 2016
Article	Thumbnail-Based Questionnaires for the Rapid and Efficient Collection of Macroseismic Data from Global Earthquakes	Rémy Bossu et al.	Seismological Research Letters Volume 88, Number 1	January/February 2017
Article	LastQuake: From rapid information to global seismic risk reduction	Rémy Bossu et al.	International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction, volume 28	24/02/18
Other publication	Seismology waveform services in EPOS	Reinoud Sleeman, Angelo Strollo, Helle Pedersen, John Clinton, Lucia Luzi, Carlo Cauzzi, Alberto Michelini, and Florian Haslinger	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Other publication	Implementing EPOS Seismology: Status and Challenges	Florian Haslinger and the EPOS Seismology team	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP9

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Newsletter article	Near Fault Observatories in Europe: the road of integration. Why do we need NFOs?	Lauro Chiaraluce, Gaetano Festa, Dragos Tataru, John Clinton, NFO Working Package	EPOS Newsletter issue 02	October 2016

Other publication	Near Fault Observatories within EPOS-IP: multidisciplinary data, high-level data products and community web services	Gaetano Festa, Lauro Chiaraluce, Hrafnhildur Valdimarsdóttir, and Semih Ergintav and the EPOS-IP WP9 working group	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
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List of publications and presentations performed by WP10

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Newsletter article	GLASS is a unique open access platform for Earth science research	Lilian Féres	The EPOS Newsletter issue 03	18/07/17
Newsletter article	The Collaboratory fo Geosciences (C4G) Plenary assembly in Coimbra, 11 July 2017	Lilian Féres	The EPOS Newsletter issue 03	18/07/17
Newsletter article	EPOS TCS GNSS Data and Products Workshop, Coimbra (Portugal), 17 - 18 January 2018	Lilian Féres	The EPOS Newsletter issue 04	02/11/17
Newsletter article	EPOS @ AGU Fall Meeting 2017, in New Orleans, Louisiana (USA), 11 - 15 December 2017	Lilian Féres	The EPOS Newsletter issue 04	02/11/17
Other publication	What is EPOS GNSS Data and Products - Conservatório TV - 6ª Edição (Narrowcasting)	Conservatório TV	Conservatório TV - 6ª Edição	24/11/17
Other publication	What is EPOS GNSS Data and Products - TVUBI (Narrowcasting)	TVUBI	TVUBI	13/12/17
Newsletter article	Noteworthy from the web - EPOS GNSS Data and Products outreach video as branded content	Lilian Féres	The EPOS Newsletter issue 05	05/02/18
Article	Evaluation of long-term BeiDou/GPS observation quality based on G-Nut/Anubis and initial results	Zhao L, Douša J, Václavovic P, Ye S, Xia F	Acta Geodyn. Geomater., Vol. 15, No. 1(189).	01/01/18
Newsletter article	Quality Controlled TCS GNSS Data and Products	Machiel Bos	The EPOS Newsletter issue 03	30/07/18
Other publication	EPOS-GNSS - Current status of service and product implementation	Rui Fernandes, Machiel Bos, Carine Bruyninx, Paul Crocker, Jan Dousa, Andrea Walpersdorf, Anne Socquet, Antonio Avallone, Athanassios Ganas, Constatin Ionescu, Ambrus Kenyeres, Benedikt Ofeigsson, Haluk Ozener, Mathilde Vergnolle, Martin Lidberg, Tomasz Liwosz, and Wolfgang Soehne and the WP10 Members	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP11

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Article	Integration of European Volcano Infrastructures	Giuseppe Puglisi, INGV, Italy; Kristin S. Vogförd, IMO, Iceland; Patrick Bachelery, IPGP, France; Teresa Ferreira, CVARG, Portugal	Volcanic Hazards, Risks and Disasters, (Elsevier Inc., 2015), edited by Paolo Papale and John F. Shroder	2015
Newsletter article	EPOS-TCS Volcano Observations makes hazard information accessible and searchable	Sara Barsotti, Fjalar Sigurðarson (IMO- ICELAND) Laura Sandri (INGV, ITALY)	EPOS Newsletter, Issue 04, Article 03	October 2017

Article	EUROVOLC - A European Network of Observatories and Research Infrastructures for Volcanology	Kristín S. Vogfjörð, Giuseppe Puglisi, Freysteinn Sigmundsson, EUROVOLC team	Millenia of Stratification between Human Life and Volcanoes: strategies for coexistence, Abstracts Volume of the International meeting 'Cities on Volcanoes 10', 2 7 September 2018, AA. VV.	September 2018
Other publication	Promotion of Earth Science through Transnational Access to the main European Volcanology Research Observatories and Infrastructures	Letizia Spampinato, Giuseppe Puglisi, and Georges Vougioukalakis	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Other publication	The contribution of the European Volcanology community to the implementation of the European Plate Observing System (EPOS) infrastructure	Giuseppe Puglisi and the EPOS-WP11 Team	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP12

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Newsletter article	Projets « ETALAB » et EPOS IP	Deschamps-Ostanciaux Emilie, CNRS, France	ForM@Ter newsletter n°13	20/09/16
Website article	From satellites via the cloud to the understanding of Earth dynamics	Michele Manunta (CNR) Salvatore Pinto (ESA)	ESA web portal	17 November 2016
Article	Ground deformation and source geometry of the August 24, 2016 Amatrice earthquake (Central Italy) investigated through analytical and numerical modeling of DInSAR measurements and structural-geological data	G. Lavecchia, R. Castaldo, R. de Nardis, V. De Novellis, F. Ferrarini, S. Pepe, F. Brozzetti, G. Solaro, D. Cirillo, M. Bonano, P. Boncio, F. Casu, C. De Luca, R. Lanari, M. Manunta, M. Manzo, A. Pepe, I. Zinno, and P. Tizzani	Geophysical Research Letters, Volume 43, n. 1, pp. 389-398	26 December 2016
Article	A Cloud Computing Solution for the Efficient Implementation of the P-SBAS DInSAR Approach	I. Zinno, F. Casu, C. De Luca, S. Elefante, R. Lanari, and M. Manunta	IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Obs. Remote Sens., pp. 1–16, 2016	March 2017
Article	Large areas surface deformation analysis through a cloud computing P-SBAS approach for massive processing of DInSAR time series	De Luca, C, Zinno, I., Manunta, M., Lanari, R., Casu, F.	Remote Sensing of Environment, Volume 202, Pages 3-17	1 December 2017
Article	Geodetic model of the 2016 Central Italy earthquake sequence inferred from InSAR and GPS data	Cheloni, D., De Novellis, V., Albano, M., Antonioli, A., Anzidei, M., Atzori, S., Avallone, A., Bignami, C., Bonano, M., Calcaterra, S., Castaldo, R., Casu, F., Cecere, G., De Luca, C., Devoti, R., Di Bucci, D., Esposito, A., Galvani, A., Gambino, P., Giuliani, R., Lanari, R., Manunta, M., Manzo, M., Mattone, M., Montuori, A., Pepe, A., Pepe, S., Pezzo, G., Pietrantonio, G., Polcari, M., Riguzzi, F., Salvi, S., Sepe, V., Serpelloni, E., Solaro, G., Stramondo, S., Tizzani, P., Tolomei, C., Trasatti, E., Valerio, E., Zinno, I., Doglioni, C.	Geophysical Research Letters, Volume 44, Issue 13, Pages 6778-6787	16 July 2017
Article	Sentinel-1 data exploitation for automatic surface deformation time-series generation through the SBAS-DInSAR parallel processing chain	I. Zinno, M. Bonano, S. Buonanno, F. Casu, C. De Luca, A. Fusco, L. Riccardo, M. Manunta, M. Manzo, and A. Pepe	in <i>International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)</i> , 2017, vol. 2017–July	July 2017
Article	Source modelling of the 2015 Wolf volcano (Galápagos) eruption inferred from Sentinel 1-A DInSAR deformation maps and pre-eruptive ENVISAT time series	V. De Novellis, R. Castaldo, C. De Luca, S. Pelel, Zinno, F. Casu, R. Lanari, G. Solaro	Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research	September 2017

Other publication	Thematic Core Service on Satellite Data of the EPOS Research Infrastructure	Michele Manunta, Francesco Casu, Ivana Zinno, Pietro Tizzani, Raffaele Castaldo, Tim Wright, Michel Diament, Emilie Ostanciaux, Mioara Manda, Jose Fernandez, Salvatore Stramondo, Christian Bignami, Philippe Bally, Salvatore Pinto, Francesco Maccaferri, and Thomas Walter	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Article	The 21st August 2017 Ischia (Italy) earthquake source model inferred from seismological, GPS and DInSAR measurements	V. De Novellis, S. Carlino, R. Castaldo, A. Tramelli, C. De Luca, N. A. Pino, S. Pepe, V. Convertito, I. Zinno, P. De Martino, M. Bonano, Giudicepietro, F. Casu, G. Macedonio, M. Manunta, C. Cardaci, M. Manzo, D. Di Bucci, G. Solaro, G. Zeni, R. Lanari, F. Bianco, and P. Tizzani	Geophysical Research Letters	August 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP13

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Website article	A New Challenge: Building Multidisciplinary Distributed Research Data Infrastructures – EPOS - European Plate Observing System	Aude Chambodut, UNISTRA, France	ICSU-Word Data System website https://www.icsu-wds.org/	07/07/16
Other publication	DOIs and Licensing for Geomagnetic Data & Products: Current Status	Aude Chambodut, UNISTRA, France	Blog of ICSU-WDS	01/02/18
Newsletter article	The Geomagnetic field between Earth's core and space: how the Geomagnetic Observations "EPOS Thematic Core Services" (TCS) address the various sources of the Geomagnetic field	Aude Chambodut, Simon Flower, Pavel Hejda, Maxim Smirnov, Alan Thomson, Ari Viljanen	The EPOS Newsletter issue 02	01/04/18
Other publication	Geo-electromagnetic data and services integration and validation in EPOS	Pavel Hejda, Simon Flower, Aude Chambodut, Juan-Jose Curto, Jürgen Matzka, Alan Thomson, Toivo Korja, Thorkild Rasmussen, Maxim Smirnov, Ari Viljanen, and Kirsti Kauristie	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP14

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal /event /...	Date/Year
Article	Preliminary results of anthropogenic seismicity monitoring in the region of Song Tranh 2 Reservoir, Central Vietnam,	Wiszniowski J, Giang NV, Plesiewicz B, Lizurek G, Van DQ, Khoi LQ, Lasocki S	Acta Geophysica	2015
Article	Platforma IS-EPOS jako nowoczesne narzędzie w badaniach sejsmiczności antropogenicznej	Lasocki S., Orlecka-Sikora B., Leptokaropoulos K., Lizurek G., Sterzel M., Szepienic T., Mutke G., and the IS-EPOS team	Zeszyty Naukowe Instytutu Gospodarki Surowcami Mineralnymi i Energią Polskiej Akademii Nauk	2016
Press release	Wzburzenie skał	Lizurek Grzegorz	Nauka online- portal magazynu Polskiej Akademii Nauk ACADEMIA © Academia nr 1 (45) 2016	2016
Press release	When ground stirs	Lizurek Grzegorz	Science Online (Web portal of a magazine of the Polish Academy of Sciences ACADEMIA)	2016
Other publication	People can cause earthquakes. Radio TOK FM Interview	Lizurek Grzegorz	Radio TOK	2016
Article	Atypical evolution of seismicity patterns resulting from the coupled natural, human-induced and coseismic stresses in a longwall coal mining environment,	Kozłowska, M., B. Orlecka-Sikora, Ł. Rudziński, Sz. Cielesta, and G. Mutke	International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences 86, 5-15,	2016

Other publication	GeoMod2008 materials benchmark: The sieve dataset.	Klinkmüller M.; Schreurs, G.; Rosenau, M.	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplementary material for analogue experiments on the interactions of two indenters, and their implications for curved fold-and-thrust-belts.	Reiter, Karsten; Kukowski, Nina; Ratschbacher, Lothar; Rosenau, Matthias	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplement to "Analogue earthquakes and seismic cycles: Experimental modelling across timescales"	Rosenau, Matthias; Corbi, Fabio; Dominguez, Stephane; Rudolf, Michael; Ritter, Malte; Pipping, Elias	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplement to: Scaling the Sand Box - Mechanical (Dis-) Similarities of Granular Materials and Brittle Rock	Ritter, Malte; Leever, Karen; Rosenau, Matthias; Oncken, Onno	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	SHEER and EPOS-IP TCS AH	Rachel Westwood	SHEER Newsletter	maggio 2016
EPOS Newsletter article	Integrated approach to geophysical hazards induced by exploration and exploitation of geo-resources – to facilitate the way of attaining excellence	Lasocki S., Orlecka-Sikora S.	EPOS Newsletter	luglio 2016
Article	IS-EPOS: a digital research space to facilitate integrated approach to anthropogenic seismic hazards	Lasocki S., Orlecka-Sikora B., Leptokaropoulos K., Sterzel M., Szepieniec T., Kocot J., Mutke G., Barański A., and the IS-EPOS team	Proceedings of 16th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, 16WCEE	13/01/2017
Article	Full moment tensor inversion as a practical tool in case of discrimination of tectonic and anthropogenic seismicity in Poland.	Lizurek G.	PAGEOPH,	gennaio 2017
Article	Time-dependent seismic hazard in Bobrek coal mine, Poland, assuming different magnitude distribution estimations,	Leptokaropoulos K., Staszek M., Cielesta S., Urban P., Olszewska D., Lizurek G	Acta Geophysica	gennaio 2017
Other publication	The European Plate Observing System & TCS Anthropogenic Hazards	Sam Toon	SHEER Newsletter	maggio 2017
EPOS Newsletter article	Seismo dance workshop	jr grasso	EPOS newsletter	ottobre 2017
Article	Clustering and Stress Inversion in the Song Tranh 2 Reservoir, Vietnam	Lizurek, G., Wiszniowski J., Van Giang N., Plesiewicz B., Van D.Q.	Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am. 107 (6): 2636-2648,	2017
Article	Temporal static stress drop variations in relation to technological activity at The Geysers geothermal field, California	Staszek, M., B. Orlecka-Sikora, K. Leptokaropoulos, P. Martinez-Garzón, and G. Kwiatek	Geophys. Res. Lett.,	2017
Presentation	Developments on the IS-EPOS Platform for Analysing Anthropogenic Hazard	Monika Sobiesiak, Stanislaw Lasocki, Beata Orlecka-Sikora, Konstantinos Leptokaropoulos, Joana Kocot, and Pawel Urban	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018
Article	Evolution of seismicity in relation to fluid injection in the North-Western part of The Geysers geothermal field.	Leptokaropoulos K., Staszek M., Lasocki S., Martinez-Garzon P., Kwiatek G	Geophysical Journal International, 212(2), 1157-1166,	2018
Other publication	EPOS (document prepared for Council of Ministers, Poland)	Orlecka-Sikora B., Lasocki S., Lizurek G., Olszewska D., Sterzel M., Chodzińska K., WP14 Team		February, 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP15

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
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EPOS Newsletter article	What is "Geological data and Modelling" TCS about?	F. Mojon Lumier (BRGM) France	EPOS Newsletter Issue N°2	October 2016
			EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP16

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Other publication	GeoMod2008 materials benchmark: The ring shear test dataset.	Klinkmüller M. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Schreurs, G. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Rosenau, M. (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplement to: Rheological benchmark of silicone oils used for analog modeling of short- and long-term lithospheric deformation.	Rudolf, Michael (Lithosphere Dynamics, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ), Potsdam, Germany); Boutelier, David (School of Environmental and Life Sciences, University of Newcastle, University Drive, Callaghan, NSW 2308, Australia); Rosenau, Matthias (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany); Schreurs, Guido (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Oncken, Onno (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	GeoMod2008 materials benchmark: The axial test dataset.	Klinkmüller M. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Schreurs, G. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Rosenau, M. (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	GeoMod2008 materials benchmark: The SEM image dataset.	Klinkmüller M. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Kenmitz H. (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany); Schreurs, G. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Rosenau, M. (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016

Other publication	GeoMod2008 materials benchmark: The sieve dataset.	Klinkmüller M. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Schreurs, G. (Institute of Geological Sciences, University of Bern, Switzerland); Rosenau, M. (Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, GFZ Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum, Potsdam, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplementary material for analogue experiments on the interactions of two indenters, and their implications for curved fold-and-thrust-belts.	Reiter, Karsten (TU Bergakademie Freiberg, Institute of Geology, Bernhard-v.-Cotta Str. 2, 09599 Freiberg, Germany); Kukowski, Nina (GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany); Ratschbacher, Lothar (TU Bergakademie Freiberg, Institute of Geology, Bernhard-v.-Cotta Str. 2, 09599 Freiberg, Germany); Rosenau, Matthias (GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplement to "Analogue earthquakes and seismic cycles: Experimental modelling across timescales"	Rosenau, Matthias (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – German Research Center for Geosciences, GFZ, Potsdam, D-14473, Germany); Corbi, Fabio (University RomaTre, Rome, I-00146, Italy); Dominguez, Stephane (University of Montpellier, UMR5243 Geosciences, Montpellier, F-34920, France); Rudolf, Michael (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, German Research Centre for Geosciences GFZ); Ritter, Malte (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, German Research Centre for Geosciences GFZ); Pipping, Elias (Free University Berlin, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Other publication	Supplement to: Scaling the Sand Box - Mechanical (Dis-) Similarities of Granular Materials and Brittle Rock	Ritter, Malte (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, German Research Centre for Geosciences GFZ); Leever, Karen (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – German Research Center for Geosciences, GFZ, Potsdam, D-14473, Germany); Rosenau, Matthias (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – German Research Center for Geosciences, GFZ, Potsdam, D-14473, Germany); Oncken, Onno (Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – German Research Center for Geosciences, GFZ, Potsdam, D-14473, Germany)	GFZ Data Services	2016
Article	Metodologia para el desarrollo de la BBDD paleomagnetica de Iberia (EPOS-DDSS Iberia paleomagnetism).	E.L. Pueyo, C. García-Lasanta, M.A. López, C. Oliván, G. San Miguel, H. Gil-Garbi, B. Oliva-Urcia, E. Beamud, R. Hernández, K. Elger, D. Ulbricht, O. Lange y el GeoKin3DPyr group	MAGIBER X-	2017

Press release	News in the Utrecht University website - Utrecht promotes interdisciplinary research into Earth's crust in Europe	Chris Spiers, Utrecht University (NL); Elisa Calignano, Utrecht University (NL)	News page in the Utrecht University Website	14/10/16
EPOS Newsletter article	From crystals to mountains: the Multi-scale laboratories Thematic Core Service (TCS)	Elisa Calignano & WP16 Team	EPOS Newsletter	01/02/17
Other publication	Rheometric measurements of salted type A gelatins	Brizzi, Silvia, Funicello, Francesca, Corbi, Fabio, Di Giuseppe, Erika, Mojoli, Giorgio	GFZ Data Services	29/09/17
Other publication	Supplement to "Work optimization predicts accretionary faulting: An integration of physical and numerical experiments"	Souloumiac, Pauline, Maillot, Bertrand, Herbert, Justin W. , McBeck, Jessica A., Cooke, Michele L.	GFZ Data Services	23/10/17
Other publication	Mechanical data and microstructures of simulated calcite fault gouge sheared at 550°C	Verberne, Berend Antonie, Chen, Jianye, Pennock, Gillian	GFZ Data Services	27/11/17
Other publication	Particle size distribution analyses of volcanic ash from Campi Flegrei (Italy) and Sakurajima (Japan) volcanoes	Del Bello, Elisabetta, Taddeucci, Jacopo, Scarlato, Piergiorgio, Giacalone, Emanuele	GFZ Data Services	01/12/17
Other publication	Hydrothermal Friction data of gouges derived from the Alpine Fault	Niemeijer, Andre	GFZ Data Services	01/12/17
Other publication	Friction data of simulated fault gouges derived from the Groningen gas field	Hunfeld, Luuk, Niemeijer, André, Spiers, Christopher	GFZ Data Services	04/12/17
Other publication	Supplement to: Sandbox Rheometry: Co-Evolution of Stress and Strain in Riedel- and Critical Wedge-Experiments	Ritter, Malte Christian, Santimano, Tasca, Rosenau, Matthias, Leever, Karen, Oncken, Onno	GFZ Data Services	07/12/17
Other publication	Experimental and model data of aggregate compaction by pressure solution	van den Ende, Martijn	GFZ Data Services	25/12/17
Other publication	Supplement to: Growing Faults in the Lab: Insights into the Scale Dependence of the Fault Zone Evolution Process	Ritter, Malte C., Rosenau, Matthias, Oncken, Onno	GFZ Data Services	25/12/17
Other publication	Dataset of Physical and Transport Property Variations Within the Carbonate-Bearing Fault Zones of the Monte Maggio Fault (Central Italy)	Trippetta, Fabio, Carpenter, Brett M, Mollo, Silvio, Scuderi, Marco M., Scarlato, Piergiorgio, Colletini, Cristiano	GFZ Data Services	25/12/17
EPOS Newsletter article	First impressions EPOS Multi-scale laboratories Trans-national access pilot program	Elisa Calignano, Emilio L. Pueyo Morer, Matthias Rosenau, Fred Beekman	EPOS Newsletter	05/02/18
Other publication	Centrifuge models investigating the influence of transverse pre-existing weaknesses on continental rifting	Corti, Giacomo; Sordi, Riccardo; Cucci, Federica	GFZ Data Services	feb-18
Other publication	Creep data of (Dotternhausen) Posidonia shale.	Rybacki, Erik; Herrmann, Johannes; Wirth, Richard; Dresen, Georg	GFZ Data Services	feb-18
Other publication	EPOS Multi-scale laboratories Data Services & Trans-national access program	Elisa Calignano and the EPOS TCS Multi-scale laboratories Team (WP16)	EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Vol 20, proceedings from the conference	8–13 April 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by WP17

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
EPOS Newsletter article	GETB Newsletter	GETB TCS	EPOS newsletter	2017

Presentation	<i>EPOS and ECCSEL: Geoenery Test Beds in European Distributed Research Infrastructures</i>	Taylor, Helen; Schofield, David; Pearce Jonathan, Vincent, Ceri	Resources for Future Generations 2018. Vancouver, Canada.	June, 2018
Presentation	In-situ Stimulation and Circulation Experiment as a Decameter Geo-Energy Test Bed for Enhanced Geothermal System Development	Jalali, Mohammadreza; Doetsch, Joseph, Gischig, Valentin; Amann, Florian; Valley, Benoit; Krietsch, Hannes; Dutler, Nathan; Villiger, Linus; Brixel, Bernard; Kittila, Anniina; Giardini, Domenico	Resources for Future Generations 2018. Vancouver, Canada.	June, 2018

List of publications and presentations performed by EPOS IP members

INGV, Italy

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Article	Al via il super laboratorio EPOS per lo studio di terremoti, vulcani e maremoti	INGV communication office	Research Italy	29/10/15
Article	Scienze della terra/ Un unico hub europeo (in Italia?) per tutti i dati "geo", intervista a Massimo Cocco	Massimo Cocco	Il sussidiario.net	03 November 2015
Article	EPOS – European Plate Observing System: Applying the VRE4EIC Virtual Research Environment Model in the Solid Earth Science Domain	Daniele Bailo, Manuela Sbarra	ERCIM News, Volume 2017	2017
Article	Una nuova infrastruttura per comprendere la dinamica del pianeta Terra	Massimo Cocco, Lilli Freda	Ricerca&Innov. ITA	July 2018
Article	Integration of heterogeneous data, software and services in Solid Earth Sciences: the EPOS system design and roadmap for the building of Integrated Core Services	Bailo, Daniele, Rossana Paciello, Riccardo Rabisoni, Manuela Sbarra, Valerio Vinciarelli	Rapporti Tecnici INGV ISSN 2039-7941, anno 2018, N. 393	2018

UiB, Norway

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Article	European Plate Observing System (EPOS): en storskala forskningsinfrastruktur i vekselvirkninger innen den faste jords fysikk (in Norwegian)	Atakan, K. (UiB, Norway)	Annual Meeting of the Norwegian Geophysical Society	21-22 October 2015
Article	European Plate Observing System (EPOS): Horizon2020 Implementation Phase Project and EPOS-Norway	Atakan, K. (UiB, Norway)	46th Nordic Seismology Seminar. Bornholm, Denmark	2015
Article	European Plate Observing System (EPOS): en storskala forskningsinfrastruktur i vekselvirkninger innen faste jords fysikk	Atakan, K. (UiB, Norway)	Annual Meeting of the Norwegian Geophysical Society	2015
Presentation	European Plate Observing System (EPOS): Implications for the Norwegian Earth Science Community	Atakan, K. (UiB, Norway)	Geo Partner Seminar Day 2016, Dep.Earth Science, UiB, Norway	11 February 2016
Presentation	Forskerens behov og systemløsninger (in Norwegian)	Atakan, K. (UiB, Norway)	Biblioteksseminar. Gardermoen, Oslo	14-15 November 2016
Presentation	EPOS-Norway: Enhancing the Solid Earth Monitoring System in the Arctic.	Kierulf, H., Atakan, K. and Ottemöller, L.	Wegener 2016 Conference, Azores, Portugal	12-15 September 2016

Presentation	European Plate Observing System (EPOS): EPOS Implementation (EPOS-IP) Project and EPOS Norway (EPOS-N) Project	Tellefsen, K. and Atakan K. (UiB, Norway)	Nordic ENVRI Seminar, Longyearbyen, Spitsbergen, Svalbard	5-7 September 2016
Presentation	European Plate Observing System – _Norway (EPOS-N)	Atakan, K., Tellefsen, K., and the EPOS.N Partners	Geopartner Seminar, Department of Earth Science, University of Bergen, Norway	16 February 2017
Presentation	European Plate Observing System – _Norway (EPOS-N): A National Consortium for the Norwegian Implementation of EPOS	Atakan, K., Tellefsen, K. and the EPOS-Norway Consortium	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria	24-28 April 2017
Presentation	Status of the European Plate Observing System (EPOS) and the Nordic Perspective	Atakan, K. (UiB, Norway)	48th Nordic Seismology Seminar and the 2nd Nordic-EPOS Meeting, Helsinki, Finland	12-16 June 2017
Presentation	European Plate Observing System – _Norway (EPOS-N)	Atakan, K., Tellefsen, K.	48th Nordic Seismology Seminar and the 2nd Nordic-EPOS Meeting, Helsinki, Finland	12-16 June 2017
Presentation	European Plate Observing System – _Norway (EPOS-N) – _GNSS and seismological data from Norway in a common e-infrastructure	Michalek, J., Langeland, T., Atakan, K., Lampe, O.D., Wang, X., Rønnevik, C., Kierulf, H.P., Kværna, T., and Roth, M.	Oral presentation in the IASPEI General Assembly, Kobe, Japan	31 July – 4 August 2017

IGF PAS, Poland

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Article	Platforma IS-EPOS jako nowoczesne narzędzie w badaniach sejsmiczności antropogenicznej	Lasocki S., Orlecka-Sikora B., Leptokaropoulos K., Lizurek G., Sterzel M., Szepienic T., Mutke G., and the IS-EPOS team (IGF PAS, Poland)	Zeszyty Naukowe Instytutu Gospodarki Surowcami Mineralnymi i Energią Polskiej Akademii Nauk	2016
Other publication	Wzburzenie skał	Lizurek Grzegorz (IGF PAS, Poland)	Nauka online- portal magazynu Polskiej Akademii Nauk ACADEMIA © Academia nr 1 (45) 2016	2016
Other publication	When ground stirs	Lizurek Grzegorz (IGF PAS, Poland)	Science Online (Web portal of a magazine of the Polish Academy of Sciences ACADEMIA)	2016
Other publication	People can cause earthquakes. Radio TOK FM Interview	Lizurek Grzegorz (IGF PAS, Poland)	Radio TOK	2016

UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT, The Netherlands

Type publication	Title of the publication	Author	Title of Journal	Date/Year
Other publication	Utrecht promotes interdisciplinary research into Earth's crust in Europe	Chris Spiers, Utrecht University (NL); Elisa Calignano, Utrecht University (NL)	Utrecht University Website	14/10/16

ANNEX 3 - List of EPOS IP events
Table 1. Overview of the EPOS Events (meetings, conference, workshop, training, brokerage events), organized by and participated by EPOS communities at M12)

LIST OF EVENTS WP1 and WP2				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS & TopoEurope	1 October 2015	Antibes, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	1st EPOS IP Project Development Board (PDB)	5 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EU H2020 VRE4EIC Kickoff Meeting	15 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	Board of Governmental Representatives teleconference	22 October 2015	teleconference	Policy Makers
Participation to a meeting	ESA GEP - Gehazard Exploitation Platform kick-off meeting	22 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EFSI Boosts Innovation!	26 October 2015	Bruxelles, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	NSF GeoPrisms	October 2015	Redondo Beach, CA, USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	GSA	November 2015	Baltimore, USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Sinoprobe	November 2015	Beijing, China	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Chinese Acad. Sci.	November 2015	Beijing, China	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	FUTUREVOLC- Final Meeting 2015	2-4 November 2015	Reykjavík, Islanda	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a meeting	FUTUREVOLC Stakeholder meeting 2015	5-6 November 2015	Reykjavík, Islanda	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGI Community Forum 2015	10 -13 November 2015	Bari, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	GNCTS Trieste	17-18 November 2015	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	1st ENVRI week	16-20 November 2015	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Statutes meeting with P.Tuinder	27 November 2015	Bruxelles, Belgium	Policy Makers
Organization of a meeting	1st EPOS IP Service Coordination Board (SCB) meeting	1 December 2015	Frankfurt, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2nd EPOS IP Project Development Board (PDB) meeting	15-16 December 2015	London, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	AGU 2015	14 December 2015	San-Francisco, CA, USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	JRU EMSO meeting	20 January 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	EUDAT User Forum and European Open Science Cloud for Research (EOSC) Workshop	3-4 February 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	European Open Science Cloud for Research (EOSC)	5 February 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EDISON - Data Infrastructure Competences and Skills Framework	8-9 February 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	VRE4EIC PEB and Technical Meeting (ENVRIplus)	15-17 February 2016	Pisa, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Open Science Retreat	22-23 February 2016	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	3rd PDB meeting teleconference	2 March 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	WP2 meeting teleconference	4 March 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	2nd Service Coordination Board meeting	18 March 2016	Prague, Czech republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	4th PDB meeting teleconference	30 March 2016		teleconference
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Board of Governmental Representatives meeting	31 March - 1 April 2016	Lisbon, Portugal	Policy Makers
Participation to a Conference	EGI Conference 2016. Opening Science in Europe and in the World	4-6 April 2016	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	MED-SUV final meeting	6-7 April 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	Ethics Working Group teleconference	11 April 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a conference	EGU General Assembly 2016; session: The European contribution to the GEO Supersite initiative (co-organized),	18 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a conference	EGU General Assembly 2016; EPOS Session SM7.1 Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences, European Geosciences Union	20 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EGU General Assembly 2016; Splinter meeting: EPOS Implementation of thematic and integrated services (public)	21 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Exhibition	EGU 2016- stand	17-22 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	EPOS IP Advisory Board teleconference	3 May 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	2nd ENVRI WEEK	9-13 May 2016	Zandvoort, Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	1st EPOS-ERIC Interim Office meeting	16 May 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	NSF CIDER	05-08 May 2016	Marconi Center, Point Reyes (CA), USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	International Seismix Symposium	15-20 May 2016	Aviemore, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	OPENAIRE NATIONAL WORKSHOP 2016	30 May 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	5th EPOS IP PDB meeting	30 May - 1 June 2016	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	IWSG 2016- International Workshop on Science Gateways	8 June 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2nd EPOS-ERIC Interim Office meeting	4 July 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	VRE4EIC MEETING	14-15 June 2016	Delft, the netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	2nd EPOS IP Ethics Working Group teleconference	23 August 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	EPOS IP SCB teleconference	1 September 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a conference	35rd General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission (GA ESC) - Session: From ORFEUS to EPOS: The development of European seismological research research infrastructures – a tribute to Torild van Eck	8 September 2016	Trieste	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	VRE4EIC PEB and Technical Meeting	8-9 September 2016	Heraklion, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	SciDataCon conference within the International Data Week: “From Big Data to Open Data: Mobilizing the Data Revolution”	11-13 September 2016	Denver, USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	6th PDB meeting	21 September 2016	Bruxelles, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Digital Infrastructures for Research 2016 conference (DI4R2016)	28-30 September 2016	Krakow, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP4

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a workshop	WP4 Legal and Governance meeting	16-17 February 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU 2016: The EPOS Legal and Governance Framework : tailoring the infrastructure to fit the needs of the EPOS services	20 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a teleconference	EPOS IP WP4 Data Policy meeting teleconference	18 May 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP5

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP WP5 meeting	09-10 May 2016	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	WP5 meeting with WP11	14 September 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP6 and WP7 (Each month the WP6 and the WP7 organize of a teleconference)

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP WP6 and WP7 team meeting	21-22 January 2016	Keyworth, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS-IP IT Meeting	23-25 May 2016	Bergen, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	ICT Proposers' Day 2016 organized by DG CONNECT	26-27 September 2016	Bratislava, Slovakia	
LIST OF EVENTS - WP8				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	HMB Messaging Service Technical Meeting - Geofon	08 -09 December 2015	Postdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS-IP WP8 Seismology, First Full Meeting	26-29 January 2016	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a workshop	Computational Seismology	29/01/16	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Workshop on structural monitoring and strong motion community in EPOS	01 March 2016	Thessaloniki, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	FDSN WGII workshop "The future of mini-SEED"	22-23 March 2017	Utrecht (NL)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	EGU 2016 - session SM7.1	20 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU 2016 - EPOS-Seismology related presentations in various sessions	17 - 22 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Workshop on structural monitoring and strong motion community in EPOS	18-19 May 2016	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2nd AHEAD meeting	29-30/06/2016	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Macroseismic intensity data exchange formats	13-14/07/2016	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	ESC 2016 - Session 2	04-11 September 2016	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	School on Seismology beyond Textbooks	29 August - 23 September 16	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	EPOS-Seismology open meeting	09 August 2016	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	ESC 2016 - open meeting on EPOS-Seismology	08 September 2016	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	Open data and software in Seismology - EIDA [Young Seismologist School on Seismology beyond Textbooks]	03 September 2016	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Workshop on SMART Cable Applications in Earthquake and Tsunami Science and Early Warning	03-04/09/16	Postdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	Open data and software in Seismology - EIDA [GFZ international Training Course in Seismology]	26 September - 21 October 2016	Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP9

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to external Governmental Event	Romanian projects and initiatives in support of ESA Earth Observation Program	11 March 2015	Magurele, Romania	National Governments
Participation to a meeting	1st EPOS IP Service Coordination Board (SCB) meeting	1 December 2015	Frankfurt, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	WP9 Meeting	18-21 January 2016	Athens, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Organization of a TCS workshop	30 January - 2 February 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Site Characterization	29 February - 2 March 2016	Thessaloniki, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS WP4 Legal & Governance Framework workshop	16-17/02/2016	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Orfeus Meeting	07 March 2016	Munich, germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	2nd SCB meeting	18 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU, Near Fault Observatories: multidisciplinary research infrastructures, high resolution data and scientific products available through dedicated services implemented within the EPOS-IP project	23–28/04/16	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	11th International Conference "Environmental Legislation, Safety Engineering and Disaster Management "	26-28 May 2016	Cluj, Romania	General Public
Participation to a Workshop	Structural Monitoring and Strong Motion Community in EPOS	17-20 May 2016	Milano, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	14th International Congress of the Geological Society of Greece	24-28 May 2016	Thessaloniki, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	EPOS-IP presentation to Greek Geoscience community	04 May 2016	Athens, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	First CARISMAND (Culture and Risk Management in Man-made and Natural Disasters) Citizen Summit held in Bucharest	9 May 2016	Bucharest, Romania	General Public
Organization of a meeting	Organization of a TCS Meeting	21-24 June 16	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to EPOS boards meeting	4nd SCB meeting	10 July 2016	Madrid	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to EPOS boards meeting	3nd SCB meeting	01 September 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	ESC 2016 - Session 2	04-11 September 2016	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP10

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP 10 Kick-off Meeting	26 October 2015	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	AGU2015 session G23C: Plate Motion, Continental Deformation, and Interseismic Strain Accumulation	14 December 2015	San Francisco, USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	EGU G6.1 - Open session on geodesy	22 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Twenty Years of EPN: Network Challenges Ahead	25-27 May 2016	San Sebastian, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Discussion with EUREF Technical Working Group on EUREF/EPOS collaboration	24 May 2016	San Sebastian, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Presentation on EUREF Permanent Network and link with EPOS WP10 activities	25 May 2016	San Sebastian, Spain	Other
Organization of a Conference	WEGENER 2016	12-15 September 2016	Ponta Delgada	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	WEGENER 2016	12-15 September 2016	Ponta Delgada	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP11				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a Workshop	Nordic participation in EPOS - Workshop held at the 46th Nordic Seismic Seminar	01 October 2015	Bornholm, Denmark	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	Building services to open access to geoscience data - EPOS	11 November 2015	University of Iceland, Reykjavík	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	WP15 workshop on borehole data	10 February 2016	Paris, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Final meeting MEDSUV project. The Geohazards Exploitation Platform	07 April 2016	Rome (Italy)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	WP5 meeting with WP11	14 September 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP12

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a Conference	GDM: a ForM@Ter service for ground deformation monitoring (talk)	13-17 April 2015	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	Training in the SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA Geohazard Exploitation Platform	15 December 2015	AGU Fall Meeting - San Francisco (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	Training in the SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA Geohazard Exploitation Platform	17 December 2015	AGU Fall Meeting - San Francisco (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	ForM@Ter, a solid Earth data pole (talk)	07 October 2015	Autrans, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EPOS IP WP12: satellite data - French contribution (poster)	12-14 October 2015	Grande Motte, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS Spain Space	17 February 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS-Italy	24 February 2016	Rome (Italy)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Final meeting MEDSUV project. The Geohazards Exploitation Platform	07 April 2016	Rome (Italy)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2016 -The Geohazards Exploitation Platform	18 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2016 - Sentinel-1 DInSAR processing chain within Geohazard Exploitation Platform	19 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2016 -Sentinel-1 automatic processing chain for volcanic and seismic areas monitoring within the Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP)	19 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2016 -The Geohazards Exploitation Platform	20 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2016 -EPOS TCS Satellite Data	20 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	EGU General Assembly 2016. Training on the SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA Geohazard Exploitation Platform	20 April 2016	EGU General Assembly 2016 - Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Final meeting MARSITE project. The Geohazards Exploitation Platform	22 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Brokerage Event	2nd TEP co-location event (ESA event). Oral presentation: GEP and EPOS	10 May 2016	Prague (Czech Republic)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Living Planet Symposium 2016. Oral presentation: On the synergic exploitation of the EPOS and GEP infrastructures: a step forward in the collaboration between Satellite and Geoscience communities	11 May 2016	Prague (Czech Rep.)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	ForM@Ter: a solid eart data and services pole (talk)	9-13 May 2016	Prague, Czech republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP13

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a Conference	International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG) meeting	01 June 2015	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	INTERMAGNET meeting	18- 20 June 2015	Niemegk, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS TCS Geomagnetic Observations Splinter Meeting	25 June 2015	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	MagNetE meeting	16-18 September 2015	Budapest, Hungary	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	sesión informativa sobre la infraestructura EPOS	18 February 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU 2016 - session SM7.1	20 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP13 Kick-off meeting	23 February 2016 to 24 February 2016	Edinburgh, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a workshop	Electromagnetic Induction Workshop	14-20 August 2016	Chiang, Thailand	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS TCS Geomagnetic Observations Splinter Meeting	09 September 2016	Dourbes, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a workshop	International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA) observatories workshop	05 September 2016	Dourbes, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	INTERMAGNET meeting	12 September 2016	Dourbes, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP14

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Other	Meeting with Minister of Higher Education for project promotion	11 September 2015	Warsaw, Poland	Policy Makers
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Seismology in France	12-14 October 2015	Montpellier, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	IS-EPOS Platform Training	November 2015	Katowice, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	Digital Research Space for Anthropogenic Hazard Studies International Conference	19-20 November 2015	Katowice, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization a Workshop	EPOS-IP WP14, Anthropogenic Seismicity Workshop.	01-02 September 2016	Nancy, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Congress of Innovation, Łódź; Keynote	06 November 2015	Łódź, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2016	17-22 April 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization the special session on induced seismicity during the international conference	IASPEI Regional Assembly Latin - American and Caribbean Seismological Commission - LACSC; "E-research platform of EPOS Thematic Core Service ANTHROPOGENIC HAZARDS" key note	20 June 2016	San Jose, Costa Rica	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Applied Geophysics	June, 2016	Gdansk, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EPOS-IP, 7th International Geosciences Student Conference	08-14 July 2016	Katowice, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization symposium on induced seismicity during the international conference	ESC2016	04-10 September 2016	Trieste, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Fluid driven seismicity: from the lab scale to field experiment	23 June 2016	Paris, France	Industry

Participation to a Workshop	Shale gas production and environmental impacts	10 June 2016	Montpellier, france	Policy Makers
Other	Job fairs EXPO II, lecture on Anthropogenic Seismicity and TCS AH.	08 April 2016	Warsaw, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Scientific picnic	25 June 2016	Olsztyn, Poland	General Public
Other	Presentation "IS-EPOS – A Web-Platform for Anthropogenic Seismicity Research"	16 February 2016	Thessaloniki, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Meeting with Director of Research and Development Center of PGNiG; collaboration possibilities discussed	01 February 2016	Warsaw, Poland	Other
Other	Promotion Materials - Informative boards on EPOS-IP and TCS AH	01 April 2016	Warsaw, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Meeting with Industry Representatives to discuss industry needs and expectations	09 May 2016	Katowice, Poland	Industry
Other	Meeting with President of Krakow for project promotion	20 January 2016	Kraków, Poland	Other
Other	Meeting with vice Minister of Environment to discuss and plan the bidirectional collaboration with the TCS AH	12 January 2016	Warsaw, Poland	Other
Other	Meeting with Director of Institute of Geophysics VAST, discussion on further collaboration with the particular attention to TCS AH and organization of a conference in Vietnam	04 April 2016	Krakow, Poland	Customers
Other	Meeting with Rector of AGH, promotion and opening of TCS to students, discussion on legal structure and further development	08 April 2016	Krakow, Poland	Customers
Other	Meeting with vice Minister of Ministry of Higher Education prof. Sirko, discussion on financial model of TCS AH platform development and	31 May 2016	Warsaw, Poland	Policy Makers

	maintenance			
Other	Meeting with Project leader of Cheshire East Council on TCS AH platform application	15 July 2016	Sandbach, UK	Customers
Participation to a Conference	„ESFRI and national research infrastructures – current challenges from perspective of V4 countries”, "An integrated approach to understanding the geophysical hazards induced by exploration and exploitation of georesources - to facilitate the way of attaining excellence" - keynote about the Thematic Core Service Antrhopogenic Hazards"	13 September 2016	Brussels	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP15

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Brokerage Event	Task 15.6 scientific drilling - ICDP data integration	11 November 2015	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	1st internal WP15 workshop	23- 25/11/2015	Copenhagen, Danemark	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	2rd internal WP15 workshop	9-10/02/2016	Paris, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	36th EGS National Delegates Meeting	17 February 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Italia - Community Coordination Meeting	24 February 2016	Roma (Italia)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	PK XML Treffen (Borehole ML)	02-03 March 2016	Weimar, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	EGU 2016	17-22 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	Intranet Webinar Participation	27 April 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	CSV Conference	03-04 May 2016	Berlin, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	OGC 3D geoscience, borehole ad hoc meeting	24 May 2016	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Geoscience Information Consortium - GIC 31st conference	24 May 2016	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	WP15 Annual meeting -hosted by ISPRA	07-09/06/ 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Geoscience Information Consortium - GIC 31st conference	20-21 June 2016	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	OGC 3D geoscience, borehole ad hoc meeting	22 June 2016	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Raising awareness and networking with scientific community	23 June 2016	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	GEO European Projects Workshop	31 May-01 June 2016	Berlin, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	35th IGC (International Geological Congress)	27 August 2016 to 04 September 2016	Capetown, South Africa	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Conference of Research Software Engineers	15-16 September 2016	Manchester, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP16

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP16 splinter meeting @ EPOS kick-off meeting	06 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	IPC meeting	07/10/15	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a meeting	Italian EPOS communities	12/10/15	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	01/12/15	Frankfurt, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EPOS-IP exhibit and slide-features at International Conference on Sustainability (Sub-theme Geo-Resources)	27 October 2015	Utrecht (NL)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Presentation of WP16 to the Spanish Community of Earth Sciences	18 February 2016	Madrid, Instituto Geográfico Nacional	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Presentation of WP16 to the Spanish Community of Volcanology	30 March 2016	Madrid, Instituto Geográfico Nacional	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	NAC 13 - Nederlands Aardewetenschappelijk Congres	07 April 2016	Veldhoven (NL)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU2016 - Poster in session SM7.1 Integrated Research Infrastructure and Services in Geosciences - EPOS WP16: A Platform for Multi-scale Laboratories	20 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Poster in session SM7.1 Integrated Research Infrastructure and Services in Geosciences - Data Services and Transnational Access for European Geosciences Multi-scale laboratories	20 April 2016	Vienna (Austria)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Meeting in Burgos with MAGIBER community	07-08 July 2016	Burgos (SP)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EPOS and WP16 presented to the Dutch Ministry of Education and Culture	06 July 2016	Den Haag (NL)	Policy Makers
Organization of a Workshop	Presentation of WP16 to the Spanish Community of Paleomagnetism (MAGIBER Network)	07-08 July 2016	Burgos (SP)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP Working package 16 is organizing a Data Service Meeting and	31 August-2 September 2016	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

	a workshop			
Participation to a Conference	SciDataCon-Advancing the Frontiers of Data in Research	11-13 september 2016	Denver, Colorado (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	Summer school on "Analogue modelling"	12-15 september 2016	Paris Orsay (FR)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Notte europea della ricerca	30 September 2016	Rome (IT)	General Public

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES performed by WP17

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase project Kick off meeting	5-7 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Preliminary WP17 Partner Meeting	14 December 2015	London, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	15-17 March 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Follow up WP17 Partner Meeting	17/03/16	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Various Harmonisation workshops	08/07/05	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES organized at National level

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ITALIA meeting	12 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ITALIA meeting	24 February 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	IRs CNR meeting	20 November 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	46th Nordic Seismology Seminar	30 September – 2 October 2015	Bornholm, Denmark	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	Annual Meeting of the Norwegian Geophysical Society (NGF årsmøte 2015)	21-22 October 2015	Os, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Geo Partner Seminar Day 2016	11 February 2016	Bergen, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Nordic ENVRI Seminar	05-07 September 2016	Spitsbergen, Svalbard	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Wegener 2016 Conference	12-15 September 2016	Azores, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Regular EPOS Slovenia meeting	10 November 2015	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Establishment of Consortium EPOS SI	4 May 2016	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	EPOS IP partner ZRC SAZU meeting	07 September 2016	Postojna, Slovenia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Other	Presentation of EPOS to OCW (Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science)	05 July 2016	The Hague (NL)	Policy Makers
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Tavolo tecnico di Coordinamento degli ERIC c/o MIUR	15 June 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EPOS Italia meeting	10 January 2017	Roma, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	FIN-EPOS- European Plate Observing System	15 December 2015	Helsinki/ Geophysical Society	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	FIRI - meeting (Finnish ESFRI projects)	28 January 2016	Espoo	Policy Makers
Participation to a Workshop	FIN-EPOS – Finnish national initiative of the European Plate Observing System	11 November 2016	Espoo/Lithosphere2016	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Pitch Event	9.VEDURSTOFA ISLANDS	22 September 2016	Ministry of Education, Reykjavík	Policy Makers

Table 2. Overview of the EPOS Events (meetings, conference, workshop, training, brokerage events) organized by and participated by EPOS communities at M24.

LIST OF EVENTS performed by WP1 and WP2				
Type of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	4th EPOS IP SCB meeting	07 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Conferenza Nazionale delle Infrastrutture di Ricerca per le Scienze della Terra Solida	12 October 2015	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Ethics Working Group meeting	13-14 October 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	1st EPOS IP BNSR meeting	17-18 October 2016	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2nd EPOS IP Advisory Board teleconference	25 October 2016	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	7th PDB meeting	03 November 2016	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	7th EPOS BGR meeting	03-04 November 2016	Vienna, Austria	Policy Makers
Exhibition	GEOXIII Plenary and Exhibition: brochures and EPOS video at the EU stand	8-10 November 2016	St Petersburg, Russia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	3rd ENVRI week	14-18 November 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	8th PDB meeting	30 November 2016	Vienna	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EPOS presented at delegation of Taiwan @ INGV in Rome	5 December 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	49th Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union (AGU)	12 - 16 December 2016	San Francisco, USA	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Conferenza Nazionale delle Infrastrutture di Ricerca per le Scienze della Terra Solida	10 January 2017	Roma, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	5th SCB teleconference	12 January 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS @ ESFRI Info Day and the Exchange of Experience Workshop	17-18 January 2017	Malaga, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EOSC pilot project kickoff meeting	17-18 January 2017	Amsterdam, the Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS Norway annual workshop	19-20 January 2017	Utrecht, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	INGV Meeting with a delegation of Thales Alenia Space	23 January 2017	Rome, Italy	Industry
Participation to a Workshop	EUDAT User Forum and European Open Science Cloud for Research (EOSC) Workshop	03-04 February 2016	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	9th PDB meeting	03 February 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	2nd CREEP Workshop: The EPOS experience: Data and Services for solid Earth Science: Open Science and Ethic Issues. Uni RomaTre	13-16 February 2017	Roma, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	8th EPOS BGR meeting	23-24 February 2017	Warsaw, Poland	Policy Makers
Organization of a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP2 meeting during TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	6th SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	10th PDB meeting	13 March 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	European Parliament for the International Women's Day - "Empowerment economico femminile: agiamo insieme! Presentation: Women in EPOS: the role of women in a large pan-European Research Infrastructure for solid Earth science	15 March 2017	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	BlueBRIDGE workshop "FAIR friendly research data catalogues: How far are we?"	03 April 2017	Barcelona, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	RDA plenary meeting	05 April 2017	Barcelona, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	11th PDB face to face meeting	05-06 April 2017	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	TF2020 Workshop on: Continuity of DCO databases, instrumentation, research consortia, and resources beyond 2020	19-20 April 2017	Florence, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EGU General Assembly 2017: EOS15, Effective Project Management in Earth Sciences – What does That Mean? (Poster session)	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Exhibition	EGU 2017- stand	23-28 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EGU General Assembly 2017; session: The GEO Geohazards Supersite initiative: improving science uptake in Disaster Risk Reduction (co-organized)	27 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EGU General Assembly 2017: session EOS7 ECS Women in geosciences	28 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	9th Meeting of the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures (GRI)	15-16 May 2017	Naples, Italy	Policy Makers
Participation to a meeting	SERA project kick-off meeting	31 May-1 June 2017	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2nd EPOS IP BNSR meeting	06-07 June 2017	Athens, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	9th EPOS Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR) meeting	07-08 June 2017	Athens, Greece	Policy Makers
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Horizon_2020 RI Support Project Meeting	08 June 2017	Brussels, Belgium	Policy Makers
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Harmonization Meeting	16-17 May 2017	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	7th SCB meeting (teleconference)	14 September 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	12th PDB meeting	20-21 September 2017	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase annual meeting	03-04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IPC meeting	04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	8th EPOS SCB meeting	06 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP3

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Harmonization Meeting	16-17 May 2017	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP4

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP5

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS WP06 and WP7

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP IT team meeting (WP6 & WP7)	04-07 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	3rd ENVRI week	14-18 November 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	W3C and VRE4EIC workshop: Smart Descriptions & Smarter Vocabularies (SDSVoc)	30 Nov - 1 Dec 2016	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP IT team meeting (WP6 & WP7)	19-21 December 2016	Utrecht, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	VRE4EIC & EVER-EST collaboration workshop	13 January 2017	Nice, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	European Open Science Cloud Pilot Project Kicks Off (EOSC)	17-18 January 2017	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EPOS-N EAB MEETING - Bergen	19-20 January 2017	Bergen, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a Workshop	EPOS Rn-Vp/Vs use-case developers team hackathon	30 January - 02 February 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	EOSC pilot WP5 kickoff meeting	21 February 2017	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	AiO meeting - ATHENS	20-22 February 2017	Athens, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP WP6 & WP7 IT-Team hackathon in Prague - 2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	27 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	42849	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS IP IT team meeting (WP6 & WP7)	09-11 May 2017	Bergen, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP IT team (WP6 & WP7) hackathon	14-16 June 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP IT team (WP6 & WP7) hackathon	11-15 September 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
	Note: each month the WP6 and the WP7 organize of a teleconference			

LIST OF EVENTS - WP8

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	ORFEUS Observatory Coordination annual Meeting 2016	25 - 28 October 2016	Dubrovnik, Croazia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a Workshop	EPOS-IP WP8-Seismology Workshop on OBS and MSP	27 - 28 October 2016	Dubrovnik, Croatia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	Open data and software in Seismology - EIDA [GFZ international Training Course in Seismology]	26. September - 21 October 2016	Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Workshop on SMART Cable Applications in Earthquake and Tsunami Science and Early Warning	3 - 4 November 2016	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EC Long-term Sustainability Stakeholders Workshop	November 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Policy Makers
Training	Open data and software in Seismology - EIDA [DESERVE Winter School]	10-11/12/16	Madaba, Jordan	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS @ ESFRI Info Day and the Exchange of Experience Workshop	17-18 January 2017	Malaga, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	First EPOS TCS-ICS harmonization meeting 16-18/05/2017 Milano	16-18/05/2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SERA Kick-off meeting	31/05-01/06/2017	Zurich, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Second EPOS TCS-ICS harmonization meeting 19-22/06/2017 Rome	19-22/06/2017	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	IAG-IASPEI 2017 - FDSN WG2 meeting	30/07-04/08/2017	Kobe, Japan	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	IAG-IASPEI 2017 - Policy issues for the European Seismological Services within EPOS	30/07-04/08/2017	Kobe, Japan	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a Workshop	Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) workshop	05-07 September 2017	Lenzburg (Switzerland)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	GFZ International training course on Seismology	04-29/09/17	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP9

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP WP09 meeting	22-24 November 2016	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to external Governmental Event	European Research Infrastructures with Romanian Participation - Environment	04 April 2017	Magurele, Romania	National Governments
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	GEO-CRADLE Regional Workshop in Romania	05 September 2017	Magurele, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	7th SCB meeting (teleconference)	14 September 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	CRL School 2017	24-26/09/2017	Corinth, Greece	

LIST OF EVENTS - WP10

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	AGU 2016: Applied automatic offset detection using HECTOR within EPOS-	16 December 2016	San Francisco, USA	scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

	IP			
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Conferenza Nazionale delle Infrastrutture di Ricerca per le Scienze della Terra Solida	10 January 2017	Roma, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Promotion of participation of EUREF to EPOS and discussion of interface between both	16 February 2017	Matera, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP10 Status and Achievements	27-28/02/2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP11

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Nordic Collaboration and Contribution to EPOS – presentation at the 47th Nordic Seismic Seminar	12 October 2016	Reykjavík, Iceland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	INGV WP11 Internal meeting	08 February 2017	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated	23-28 /04/2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

	Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences			
Organization of a conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; session: The GEO Geohazards Supersite initiative: improving science uptake in Disaster Risk Reduction (co-organized)	23-28 /04/2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	IAVCEI 2017 Scientific Assembly	14-18 August 2017	Portland, Oregon, U.S.A	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	9th SCB meeting	10 June 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	The EPOS TCS "Volcano Observations" (EPOS IP Working Package 11) meeting	07-08 September 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS WP12

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	SARwatch. Oral Presentation to present the EPOSAR service: Automatic and Systematic Sentinel-1 SBAS-DInSAR Processing Chain for Deformation Time-series Generation	5-7 october 2016	Porto (Portugal)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	SARwatch. The Sentinel-1 SBAS web tool for advanced DInSAR analyses through the ESA Geohazard Exploitation Platform (GEP)	5-7 october 2016	Porto (Portugal)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Workshop Supra National Ground Motion Service BGR Hanover	02-03 November 2016	Hanover (Germany)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	AGU 2016. Oral Presentation (G33C-04) to present the EPOSAR service: Massive Cloud Computing Processing of P-SBAS Time Series for Displacement Analyses at Large	12-16 December 2016	San Francisco (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

	Spatial Scale			
Participation to a Conference	AGU 2016. Poster: (G23A-1038): Massive Cloud Computing Processing of P-SBAS Time Series for Displacement Analyses at Large Spatial Scale	12-16 December 2016	San Francisco (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Brokerage Event	DIAS Industry Information Day	20 December 2016	Frascati (Italy)	Industry
Participation to a Workshop	EPOS-Italy	10 January 2017	Rome (Italy)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	SBAS-DInSAR processing on the GEP	25 January 2017	Zurich (Switzerland)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP13

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	Workshop CzechGeo/EPOS	16 November 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP WP13 Meeting	25/11/2016	Helsinki, Finland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	WP13 Workshop	28 February 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Intermagnet Annual Meeting: EPOS IP Progress (oral)	3-5/09/2017	Hermanus, Republic of South Africa	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	IAPSO - IAMAS - IAGA joint Assembly: EPOS IP Progress (oral)	27/08-1/09/2017	Cape Town, Republic of South Africa	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP14

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	AGIS 2016 Hannover	22-23/11/2016	Hannover, germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	16th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering	09 January 2017	Santiago, Chile	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS TCS Anthropogenic Hazards annual meeting	11-12 May 2017	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS TCS Anthropogenic Hazards IS-EPOS Platform Workshop	12 May 2017	Potsdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	9th SCB meeting	10 June 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	IAG-IASPEI 2017: IS-EPOS e-Platform of EPOS Thematic Core Service Anthropogenic Hazards - a virtual laboratory for collaborative research experimentation	30/07-04/08/2017	Kobe, Japan	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Café LabEx	29-09-2017	Strasbourg, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP15				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	2nd Service Coordination Board meeting, Madrid 7 October 2016	07/10/2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EPOS Sweden hearing : round table with informal presentations and discussion	24 October 2016	Uppsala (Sweden)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Conference	EPOS IP presentation to Nordic GIC	24-25 October 2016	Copenhagen (Denemark)	Other
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP WP15 TCS Geological information and modelling meeting	22-23 November 2016	Postdam, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	RDA-Deutschland-Treffen	28-29 November 2016	Potsdam	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS Italia - Community Coordination Meeting	10 January 2017	Roma (Italia)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	3rd Service Coordination Board meeting	12/01/2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS France - Community Coordination Meeting	17 January 2017	Paris (France)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	38th EGS National Delegates Meeting	13-14 February 2017	Brussels(Belgium)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	Metadata for 3D geological models - technical workshop	22-23 February 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	OGC Earth Systems Science DWG (ESS DWG) – proposal for a GeoScience DWG	23 March 2017	Delft (The Netherlands)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	23-28/04/2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Working Group for the Borehole Markup Language of the German State Geological Surveys	22 – 23/05/2017	Nurnberg, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Geoscience Information Consortium - GIC 31st conference	24 May 2017	Dublin (Ireland)	Other
Participation to a Workshop	OGC GeoSciML SWG annual workshop	29/05/2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Geoscience Information Consortium - GIC 32nd conference	30/05/2017	Vienna, Austria	Industry
Participation to a meeting	9th SCB meeting	10 June 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd Nordic EPOS meeting	14-16/06/2017	Helsinki, Finland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	INSPIRE CONFERENCE	4/8 Sept. 2017	Kehl, Germany & Strasbourg, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	39th EGS National Delegates Meeting	05 September 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	OGC Technical and Planning Committee Meeting	14 September 2017	Southampton , UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting				

LIST OF EVENTS - WP16

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	GEOMOD2016 - Oral presentation EPOS Thematic session: General Intro to EPOS IP and TCS Multi-scale laboratories (Elisa Calignano)	17-21 october 2016	Montpellier, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	GEOMOD2016 - Poster presentation: EPOS Multi-scale laboratories platform: a long-term reference tool for experimental Earth Sciences (Daniele Trippanera et al.,)	17-21/10/2016	Montpellier, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EPOS-IP exhibit and slide-features at International Conference on Sustainability, 2016 Edition (Sub-theme Geo-Resources) - Poster - EPOS WP16: A Platform for Multi-scale Laboratories	28 October 2016	Utrecht (NL)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	WP16 Utrecht Team meets Dutch BNSR and BGR representatives	01 November 2016	Utrecht (NL)	Policy Makers
Participation to a meeting	Licensing teleconference	10/11/16	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	WP6&7	19-21/12/2016	Utrechth, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Splinter meeting held at the TSG/VMSG/BGA joint assembly	06/01/17	Liverpool, UK	
Participation to a meeting	Geoscience faculty members concerned with analogue modelling	31/01/17	Hamburg, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	DI4R2017 "CONNECTING THE BUILDING BLOCKS FOR OPEN SCIENCE"	01/02/17	Brussels(Belgium)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	WP16 Utrecht Team meets Dutch BNSR and BGR representatives	10 February 2017	Utrecht (NL)	Policy Makers
Participation to a Conference	CREEP meeting	13-17/02/2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP WP16 ,TCS Multi-scale laboratories meeting	15-16 February 2017	Utrecht, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Harmonization group 9	27/02/17	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS-Spain meeting	23/05/17	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	20/06/17	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	3rd EPOS Volcanology WP11 SPAIN	29/06/17	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Workshop	SUBITOP 2nd workshop	11/07/17	Utrecht, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	Primer Congreso en Ingenieria Geomatica	05/07/17	Valencia, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Reunion de la Comision de Paleomagnetismo de la Sociedad Geologica de Espana	15/09/17	Valle del Grio, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP17

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP Implementation Phase Council meeting	05-06 October 2016	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	2nd EPOS IP Project: TCS - ICS Integration Workshop	28 February-2 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	5st SCB meeting	03 March 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2017; EPOS Session(co-organized) on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences	24 April 2017	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	GETB Community Workshop	18-19 April 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS organized at National level				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ITALIA meeting	10 January 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop	19-20 January 2017	Bergen, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2nd regional Nordic EPOS meeting	14-16 June 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ITALIA meeting	12 September 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Pitch Event	9.VEDURSTOFA ISLANDS	13 February 2017	Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources, Reykjavík	Policy Makers

Table 3. Overview of the EPOS Events (meetings, conference, workshop, training, brokerage events), organized by and participated by EPOS communities at M36

LIST OF EVENTS performed by WP1 and WP2				
Type of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase annual meeting	03-04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IPC meeting	04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	8th EPOS SCB meeting	06 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase Project Advisory Board meeting	09-nov-17	Paris, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Project Development Board (PDB) meeting	23 - 24 Nov 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	10th EPOS Board of Governmental Representatives meeting	14-15 December 2017	Berlin, Germany	Policy Makers
Participation to a Conference	American Geophysical Union (AGU) 2017 Fall Meeting	11-15 December 2017	New Orleans, Louisiana (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Project Development Board (PDB) teleconference	28 February 2018	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	12-14 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Service Coordination Board (SCB) meeting	14 march 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Board of National Scientific Representatives (BNRS) meeting	15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP Project Development Board (PDB) teleconference	<u>04 April 2018</u>	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS @ the 6th ENVRI week	14-18 May 2018	Zandvoort, Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	11th EPOS Board of Governmental Representatives meeting	21-22 May 2018	Bratislava, Slovakia	Policy Makers
Organization of a meeting	EPOS INFO-DAY in the Eastern Adriatic Area	29-30 May 2018	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS TCS-ICS INTERACTION meeting	4-6 June 2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	15th EPOS PDB meeting	18-19 June 2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	1st EPOS External Evaluation Panel meeting	18-19 June 2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS workshop and Table ronde during Cities on Volcanoes (CoV10) IAVCEI conference	2 September 2018	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS ICS hackathon during the EPOS Implementation and Validation Workshop	12 - 15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS data and service provision Validation Phase: the EPOS External Evaluation Panel meeting	18-19 June 2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS ICS hackathon	19-21 June 2018	Utrecht, (The Netherlands)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS @ Geoethics Outcomes and Awareness Learning workshop	30 July – 3 August 2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	ESC GA 2018	2 - 7 September 2018	Valletta, Malta	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	10th edition of Cities on Volcanoes (CoV10) IAVCEI conference	2 - 7 September 2018	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS presented to a scientific delegation of Chile & Argentina @ INGV headquarters	4 September 2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS @ the launch of the 2018 ESFRI Roadmap in Vienna	11 September 2018	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP3

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase annual meeting	03-04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP4				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase annual meeting	03-04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP5				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase annual meeting	03-04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS WP06 and WP7				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Implementation Phase annual meeting	03-04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ICS hackathon	19-21 June 2018	Utrecht, (The Netherlands)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
	Note: each month the WP6 and the WP7 organize of a teleconference			

LIST OF EVENTS - WP8

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a Workshop	Internet Macroseismology	14-15/11/2017	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS Seismology workshop	25- 27 October 2017	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	2017 European OBS technical workshop	06-7 November 2017	Paris, France	
Participation to external Scientific Event	EIDA Iberia	8-9/03/2018	Madrid, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to external Scientific Event	OGC TC/PC Geoscience Domain Working Group	19-23/03/2018	Orleans, france	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018; EPOS Session	8-13 April 2018	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	ESC GA 2018	1-7 September 2018	Valletta, Malta	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	ESC GA 2018	1-7 September 2018	Valletta, Malta	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP9				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Strain Meter Array (STAR) meeting	16-17 October 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP WP09 IT Hackathon Meeting	12-14/02/2018	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS TCS Near-Fault Observatories (NFO) plenary meeting	4 – 5 July 2018	Patras, Greece	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP10				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	9th SCB meeting	10 June 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Brief presentation about EPOS GNSS Data and Products and Solid Earth Science	24 November 2017	Covilhã, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS TCS GNSS Data and Products Workshop	16-17 January 2018	Coimbra, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EUREF AC Workshop: Galileo-capability of the EUREF Permanent Network	25-26/10/2017	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EUREF AC Workshop: Management and dissemination of GNSS site log metadata using the new GeodesyML standard	25-26/10/2017	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EUREF AC Workshop: Towards an Official EPN Densification Product	25-26/10/2017	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EUREF AC Workshop: New Multi-year EPN Solution Expressed in IGS14	25-26/10/2017	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EUREF AC Workshop: Update on the new EPOS GNSS metadata management system presented at EUREF analysis centers workshop in Brussels	25-26/10/2017	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	EUREF AC Workshop: G-Nut/Anubis - a tool for Multi-GNSS data quality control (Tutorial)	25-26/10/2017	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Colloque G2 2017 Géodésie – Rhéologie 2017: Massive GNSS processing in double difference in the framework of the EPOS-IP project	13-15/11/2017	Nice, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	AGU Fall Meeting 2017: The Contribution for Improving GNSS Data and Derived Products for Solid Earth Sciences Promoted by EPOS-IP	11-15/12/2017	New Orleans, Louisiana	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP11

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
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Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	TCS organisation and discussions	29-30/11/2017	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EUROVOLC Kick-off meeting	4-9 February 2018	Kevlavik, Iceland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Implementation and Validation Workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	10th edition of Cities on Volcanoes (CoV10) IAVCEI conference	2 - 7 September 2018	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a Workshop	EPOS workshop and Table ronde during Cities on Volcanoes (CoV10) IAVCEI conference	2 September 2018	Naples, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS WP12

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP12 Satellite data meeting	20/10/2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Training	SBAS-DInSAR processing on the ESA Geohazard Exploitation Platform	24 November 2017	Tenerife, Spain	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP12 Satellite data meeting	06 December 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	AGU 2017	12-13/12/2017	New Orleans, USA	
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	08 January 2018	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	WP12 Satellite data meeting	8-9/02/2018	Paris, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	14 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP13

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	IMAGE Meeting: EPOS: role to IMAGE and data dissemination	11-12/10/2017	Niemegk, Germany	
Participation to a meeting	9th SCB meeting	10 June 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS IP WP13 Meeting	12 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	3rd BNSR Meeting	13 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP14

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	IPR & Data Policy Splinter Meeting	04 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGW2017: The CDGP, data center for deep geothermal energy in Alsace	12-13/10/2017	Karlsruhe, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	VIET-GEOPHYS-2017 The International Conference on Research Development and Cooperation in Geophysics	18-22/10/2017	Hanoi, Vietnam	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	RaSiM, 9th Int. Symp. on Rockbursts and Seismicity in Mines – RaSiM9	15-17/11/2017	Santiago, Chile	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Conslutations (Polish team) - management meetings	11 December 2017	Krakow, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Conslutations (Polish team) - management meetings	11 December 2017	Krakow, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SHEER Project Stakeholders Meeting	16/01/2018	Keele, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Conslutations (Polish team) - management meetings	22 January 2018	Krakow, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	Conslutations (Polish team) - management meetings	12 February 2018	Krakow, Poland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	14 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	COST TIDE: IS-EPOS: Development, current status and future challenges	21-22/03/2018	Bologna, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS-IP Seismology Harmonization meeting	16-18/05/2017	Milan, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS BGR meeting	07-08/06/2018	Athens, Greece	Policy Makers

Organization of a meeting	EPOS TCS Antropogenic Hazard (WP14) Annual Meeting and Workshop	11-14 June 2018	<u>Oulu, Finland</u>	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP15				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB Meeting	06/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Journées Evolen: "Towards great infrastructures of geoscientific data") in Session 6 = Innovations and developments in Geosciences	17/10/2017	Paris, France	Industry
Participation to a meeting	Pôle Avenia - Club d'innovation forage-puits et monitoring -	21/11/2017	Paris, France	Private sector
Organization of a meeting	106th OGC TC -	19-23/03/2018	Orléans, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB Meeting	16/03/2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Open Day at 106th Open Geospatial Consortium Technical Committee: Title "From space to underground, data and services for Territories Mgt". Presentations, demonstrations, round tables, with a slot on innovative data and services infrastructures including a presentation of EPOS .	19-23/03/2018	Orléans, France	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	University lectures summer semester 2018 - lecture by about scientific infrastructures using the example of EPOS + demos	summer 2018	Berlin, Germany	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
LIST OF EVENTS - WP16				
Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	IPC meeting	04/10/17	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	06/10/17	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS Multi-scale laboratories meetings	23-24 October 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Swiss Geoscience meeting: The Swiss participation to a network of Multi-scale laboratories: EPOS-MSL	17/11/17	Davos, Switzerland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	BGS Internal EPOS meeting	28/11/17	Keyworth, UK	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Utrecht University Friday Earth Science Talk	08/12/17	Utrecht, The Netherlands	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS IP TCS-ICS integration and validation workshop	11-15 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	08/01/2018	08 January 2018	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	TCS TNA Coordination Team meeting	15/01/18	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	TCS TNA Coordination Team MSL meeting	18/01/18	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a meeting	TCS TNA Coordination Team meeting	01/03/18	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation workshop	12/03/18	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	IT hackaton	13/03/18	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	SCB meeting	14/03/18	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS - WP17

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Participation to a meeting	2nd EPOS annual meeting	3-4/10/2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	EPOS Validation Workshop	04-05 October 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP17 Team Meeting	03 November 2017	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	9th SCB meeting	10 June 2017	Bucharest, Romania	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	WP17 Team Meeting	25 January 2018	teleconference	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a Conference	EGU General Assembly 2018	08-13 April 2018	Vienna, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Implementation and Validation Workshop in Lisbon	12 - 14 March 2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Participation to a meeting	Resources for Future Generations 2018	16 - 21/06/18	Vancouver, Canada	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

LIST OF EVENTS organized at National level

Types of activity	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ITALIA meeting	10 January 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)

Organization of a Workshop	EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop	19-20 January 2017	Bergen, Norway	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	2 nd regional Nordic EPOS meeting	14-16 June 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Organization of a meeting	EPOS ITALIA meeting	12 September 2017	Rome, Italy	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Pitch Event	9.VEDURSTOFA ISLANDS	13 February 2017	Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources, Reykjavík	Policy Makers